

Life Cycle Assessment of MIL-100(Fe): diagnosis and comparison with traditional filters

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Abstract

This thesis presents a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the large-scale production of the metal–organic framework MIL-100(Fe), aiming to evaluate its environmental sustainability and identify main impact hotspots. This study is part of the European SIMIACCI project, which seeks to deploy MIL-100(Fe) as a sustainable air filtration material for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAMs), competitive with traditional filters, such as High-Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) filters composed of glass fibres, or Minimum Efficiency Reporting Value (MERV-13) filters based on polypropylene granulate.

The environmental assessment was modelled in SimaPro, following the Life Cycle Assessment methodology and applying the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method. Laboratory and pilot-scale data were combined with literature sources and Ecoinvent v3.9.1 datasets to ensure data completeness and representativeness.

Results show that the reaction and drying stages are responsible for the highest environmental impacts, mainly due to chemical reagent use, water consumption, and steam demand. Energy recovery, solvent-free synthesis routes, and renewable energy integration are identified as key strategies to enhance process sustainability. MIL-100(Fe) production shows higher impacts than materials used in traditional filters, though this is largely attributed to the greater maturity and optimisation of conventional processes. Nevertheless, this work focuses solely on the material production, while potential advantages of MIL-100(Fe) are expected during filter operation and maintenance.

Overall, the study provides the first quantitative assessment of the environmental footprint of MIL-100(Fe) at scale-up level, offering insights for process optimisation and supporting the development of next-generation, low-impact filtration systems for cultural heritage preservation.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment, MIL-100(Fe), Metal–Organic Frameworks, Sustainable air filtration, Cultural heritage preservation

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List of Acronyms

BTC	Benzene-1,3,5-Tricarboxylate Acid
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CCIs	Cultural and Creative Industries
CCS	Cultural and Creative Sector
CFC	Chlorofluorocarbon
CHIs	Cultural Heritage Institutions
CTU_e	Comparative Toxic Units for Ecosystems
CTU_h	Comparative Toxic Units for Humans
EF	Environmental Footprint
EPRS	European Parliamentary Research Service
E_{steam}	Total Energy Associated with Steam
FU	Functional Unit
g	Grams
g/mol	Grams Per Moles
GLAMs	Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HEPA	
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
ICOM	International Council of Museums
IN	Input
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
kBq U-235 eq	Kilobecquerels of Uranium-235 Equivalents
kg	Kilograms
kg CFC-11 eq	Kg CFC-11 Equivalents
kg CO₂ eq	Kg CO ₂ -Equivalents
kg N eq	Kg of Nitrogen Equivalents
kg NMVOC eq	Kg of Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds Equivalents
kg Sb eq	Kilograms of Antimony Equivalents

kg/year	Kilograms per Year
kJ/kg	Kilojoules per Kilograms
KPt	Kilo points
kton	Kiloton
kton/year	Kiloton per Year
kWh	Kilo Watt-Hour
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
m	Mass
m³	Cubic Meters
m³ world eq	Cubic Meters World Equivalents
MB	Material Balance
MERV	Minimum Efficiency Reporting Value
MIL-100(Fe)	Materials From Institut Lavoisier-100(Iron)
MJ	Megajoules
MJ/year	Megajoules per Year
MOF	Metal-Organic Framework
MOFs	Metal-Organic Frameworks
mol	Moles
mol H⁺ eq	Moles of Hydrogen Ion Equivalents
mol N eq	Moles of Nitrogen Equivalents
\dot{m}_{steam}	Annual Steam Mass Flow
MW	Molecular Weight
NMVOC	Non-Methane Volatile Organic Compounds
ODP	Ozone Depletion Potential
OUT	Output
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PHBV	Poly(3-Hydroxybutyrate-Co-3-Hydroxyvalerate)

PM	Particulate Matter
RER	Europe
SIMIACCI	Sustainable Intelligent Management of Indoor Air Quality for the Culture and Creative Industries
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SMEs	Small And Medium-Sized Enterprises
SS	Single Score
STY	Space-Time Yield
SVOCs	Semi-Volatile Organic Compound
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds
Wh	Watt-Hours
WP	Work Package
Y	Yield
Δh_v	Specific Enthalpy of Saturated Steam

1 Introduction

1.1 Problem contextualisation

The preservation of cultural heritage represents a major societal challenge, particularly in environments that house sensitive artefacts such as Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAMs). These spaces must maintain strict environmental conditions to prevent the degradation of valuable collections. Airborne pollutants, such as volatile organic compounds (VOCs), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and hydrogen sulphide (H₂S), can accelerate the deterioration of both organic and inorganic materials, even at concentrations much lower than those acceptable in standard indoor environments [1], [2]. Current air purification technologies, although effective at removing particulates, often fail to adequately capture gaseous contaminants and typically entail significant energy and maintenance costs [3]. Therefore, innovative solutions are required to ensure the protection of cultural heritage while aligning with broader environmental sustainability goals.

In this context, the European project SIMIACCI (Sustainable Intelligent Management of Indoor Air Quality for the Culture and Creative Industries) [1] aims to develop advanced systems for sustainable indoor air management. One of its main technological frontiers is the application of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), crystalline materials composed of metal ions and organic linkers forming highly porous structures capable of adsorbing a wide variety of pollutants [4]. Among these, MIL-100(Fe), where MIL stands for Material from Institut Lavoisier [5], is an iron-based MOF that has attracted significant interest due to its high surface area, structural robustness and strong affinity for VOCs and other contaminants under real operating conditions [6]. Its potential implementation in GLAM environments could lead to improved air quality, lower energy consumption and longer preservation times for artefacts [1].

However, to ensure that these solutions contribute positively to climate goals and to achieve widespread adoption, it is essential to understand their environmental footprint. Until now, studies on the environmental impacts of MIL-100(Fe) production have been limited to laboratory-scale assessments, often neglecting issues of scalability and industrial applicability. [7]. This creates a significant gap in sustainability evaluation, which is critical given the projected expansion of MOFs in commercial and institutional settings. Furthermore, as attention on the environmental performance of materials and processes used in emerging green technologies grows [8], it becomes crucial to assess whether the benefits of MOFs in air purification outweigh the environmental costs of their production.

A comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) can provide this evaluation. A LCA represents a robust framework for identifying the stages of a production process that have a significant impact on the environment and propose improvements based on their impact. In a LCA the inputs and outputs of each stage (from raw materials to disposal or end-of-life) are analysed identifying which have a significant impact, also called hotspots [9], [10]. This study aims to bridge the knowledge gap by moving from the

laboratory context to a realistic industrial-scale analysis, offering valuable insights to researchers, policymakers and industry stakeholders.

1.2 Dissertation's main objectives

The aim of this thesis is to conduct a Life Cycle Assessment of the industrial-scale production of MIL-100(Fe) in order to quantify its environmental impact and to identify the main environmental hotspots within the synthesis process. This study provides an accurate profile of the environmental footprint of MIL-100(Fe) by shifting the production process from a laboratory-scale to an industrial scale scenario. The results will contribute to a better understanding of whether MIL-100(Fe) can be considered an environmentally sustainable option for air purification in GLAMs and propose eventual improvement to an industrial-scale production process to reduce its environmental footprint.

Furthermore, the environmental performance of this metal–organic framework will be compared with that of conventional filtration technologies currently employed in GLAMs, such as High-Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) and Minimum Efficiency Reporting Value (MERV-13) filters [11]. This comparison will help determine whether MIL-100(Fe) can represent a more sustainable alternative for indoor air purification and provide recommendations for its implementation or for improving industrial-scale production processes. Finally, the study contributes to the broader objectives of the SIMIACCI project by providing insights for process optimization and by fostering sustainable innovation in indoor air quality management.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

This master's thesis is organised into six chapters that reflect the logical progression of the research:

- **1 Introduction:** This chapter outlines defines the research problem and introduces the main objectives of the project. Lastly, it presents the thesis structure.
- **2 Background and Context:** This chapter provides an overview of the SIMIACCI project and discusses the relevance of MOFs in indoor air purification, emphasizing the role and the potential of MIL-100(Fe) and the challenges of scaling up from laboratory to industrial production.
- **3 Literature Review:** The third chapter reports a review of the theoretical framework related to sustainability and environmental assessments, focusing specially on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology. It includes a detailed literature review addressing the current state of LCA applications in MOF production, particularly MIL-100(Fe), identifying existing knowledge gaps and methodological considerations.
- **4 Methodology:** The fourth chapter presents the methodology adopted in this thesis. The structure of LCAs performed is described in detail, including goal and scope definition, inventory data, assumptions and the final interpretation.
- **5 Results and Discussion:** In this chapter, the obtained results of the LCAs are presented and critically discussed in relation to existing literature and environmental performance indicators.

- **6 Conclusions:** The final chapter summarizes the key results of the thesis, including also its limitations and implications. At the end, it also outlines potential future developments of the projects within the SIMIACCI framework.

2 Background and context

This chapter presents the contextual background and motivation behind this study, focusing on Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) challenges in cultural heritage environments and on the technological innovation proposed by the SIMIACCI project (Figure 1). It begins with an overview of the GLAM sector, followed by a discussion of air pollution issues and current mitigation technologies. It then introduces SIMIACCI and the role of this thesis in assessing the environmental performance of MIL-100(Fe) production.

Figure 1: Logo of the SIMIACCI project, focused on the development of sustainable air filtration solutions for cultural heritage preservation in GLAM environments. [1]

2.1 The Cultural and Creative Industries and the role of GLAMs

Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) constitute a significant component of the European economy, encompassing industries related to heritage, archives, libraries, museums, performing and visual arts, architecture, design, publishing and media. Between 2013 and 2020, the value added of these sectors grew at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 4.3% [12]. In terms of employment, approximately 8.15 million people were working in the Cultural and Creative Sector (CCS) in 2020, representing 6.3% of total employment across the studied countries [12]. Furthermore, CCS enterprises accounted for 12.4% of all active businesses in the region, underlining their importance not only culturally but also economically [12].

Within this broader framework, GLAM institutions represent a foundational pillar of the cultural infrastructure. They ensure the preservation, accessibility, and dissemination of tangible and intangible heritage, thereby fostering education, innovation and social cohesion. Among the GLAM institutions and CCS we refer to two examples of sub-sectors, highlighting their relevance: the Books and Press segment, which includes publishing, printing and related activities, generated € 56.2 billion of value added in 2020 ($\approx 0.8\%$ of total economic output) and employed 1.43 million workers [12]. Similarly, the Visual Arts sector, which includes galleries, exhibitions and art spaces, contributed € 31.6 billion ($\approx 0.5\%$ of the total EU economy) and employed 1.1 million people in 2020 [12].

These figures demonstrate that GLAMs not only act as custodians of cultural memory but also as economic and innovation drivers within the European CCIs. Their mission of safeguarding cultural assets also exposes them to specific challenges, particularly regarding the control of indoor air quality, a key determinant of material preservation and operational sustainability, aspects that are at the core of the SIMIACCI project discussed in this work.

2.2 Indoor Air Quality challenges in GLAMs

Indoor Air Quality plays a crucial role in the preservation of cultural heritage collections and in the comfort and safety of staff and visitors. GLAM environments are particularly sensitive to air pollutants due to the organic and semi-organic nature of most artefacts, which makes them highly reactive to chemical and physical degradation processes [13]. Unlike conventional buildings, heritage spaces often lack flexibility in environmental control, as conservation needs must coexist with architectural, aesthetic and operational constraints. For instance, libraries and archives hold vast collections of books and manuscripts composed of cellulose-based materials such as paper, wood and certain textiles, as well as synthetic polymers used in book bindings and covers. Additionally, these objects contain complex assemblies of inks, dyes, pigments, binders, adhesives and other compounds that are particularly prone to chemical deterioration [14]. The preservation of these materials relies heavily on maintaining optimal environmental conditions. Historically, preventive conservation efforts have focused on controlling physical parameters such as temperature, relative humidity, light exposure, biological contamination and ventilation quality. [15] However, recent research emphasized the significant role of air pollutants, both of outdoor and indoor origin, in accelerating the degradation processes of cultural materials. These pollutants, often imperceptible, can initiate or accelerate chemical reactions that compromise the integrity of artefacts.

Among the primary outdoor pollutants that pose a threat to Cultural Heritage Institutions (CHIs) there are sulphur dioxide (SO_2), nitrogen oxides (NO and NO_2 , collectively referred to as NO_x), ozone (O_3), reduced sulphur compounds such as hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) and various volatile organic compounds (VOCs) [14], [16]. These substances typically arise from vehicular emissions, industrial activities and fossil fuel combustion. Once they enter indoor spaces through natural or mechanical ventilation, they can interact with sensitive heritage materials, accelerating degradation processes such as acid hydrolysis, photochemical reactions and oxidation. Sulphur and nitrogen oxides are particularly hazardous as they react with moisture in the air to form strong acids, which can corrode materials such as paper, pigments, textiles and metals. Ozone, a highly reactive oxidant, is known to cause dyes to fade and organic fibres to weaken. Furthermore, VOCs such as benzene, toluene and xylene, which are common in urban areas with high traffic density, are often detected indoors and can contribute to the formation of secondary pollutants through chemical reactions [14].

Indoor-generated pollutants can be equally damaging. For example, VOCs are emitted from a variety of sources within cultural heritage institutions, including building materials, wooden furniture, adhesives, cleaning products and even the artefacts themselves [7], [8]. VOCs are of particular concern not only due to their harmful effects on collections but also because of their health implications in short and long periods of time. The European Community defines the organic compounds that evaporate under ambient conditions of 25°C and vapour pressure greater than 0.01 kPa to be part of the VOCs [7], [17]. Their presence is ubiquitous in indoor air and is associated with a wide range of health risks, including respiratory and carcinogenic effects [18]. Notably, formic and acetic acids are released from cellulose-based and wood composite objects and they are particularly damaging to paper and textiles due to their

acidity. Formaldehyde, another prevalent VOC, is known to cause the yellowing and embrittlement of paper-based materials [7]. Semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs), carbonyl compounds and low molecular weight acids may also be released from synthetic materials used in display cases or conservation treatments. Even particulate matter (PM), which is less frequently studied in cultural contexts, can enhance the damaging effects of VOCs by acting as a transport medium or reactive surface [7].

The complexity of pollutant interactions, combined with fluctuating microclimatic conditions, makes IAQ management in GLAMs a demanding task. Traditional strategies rely heavily on ventilation and air conditioning systems, which, although effective at diluting pollutants, often entail high energy consumption and limited selectivity [18]. Moreover, such systems are seldom tailored to the unique requirements of heritage preservation, where silent operation, visual discretion and chemical neutrality are essential. Consequently, there is an increasing demand for innovative filtration materials and energy-efficient purification technologies capable of removing both particulate and gaseous pollutants without compromising the integrity of collections or the sustainability of museum operations.

2.3 Existing air filtration and climate control solutions

The preservation of cultural heritage collections in GLAM institutions requires efficient air filtration and climate control systems capable of maintaining both clean air and stable environmental conditions. Traditionally, this has been achieved through Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems [19] combined with mechanical filtration technologies, whose main purpose is the removal of airborne particulate matter and, to a lesser extent, gaseous pollutants. HVAC systems are integrated technologies designed to regulate indoor temperature, humidity and air quality, ensuring thermal comfort for occupants while maintaining a healthy and stable environment [19].

Among the most widely used filtration systems in heritage buildings are High-Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA) and Minimum Efficiency Reporting Value (MERV) filters, that are shown in Figure 2. These filters are standardized according to their ability to capture suspended particles of varying sizes, which can include dust, soot, pollen, biological contaminants and other aerosols that contribute to the deterioration of artworks and archival materials [20], [21].

HEPA filters, originally developed for use in cleanrooms and medical environments, are designed to remove at least 99.97% of airborne particles higher or equal than 0.3 μm in diameter [22], [23], [24], [25]. They operate primarily through mechanical mechanisms such as interception, impaction and diffusion, relying on dense fibre mats that force air through a tortuous path, where particles are trapped. While their filtration efficiency is extremely high, HEPA filters exhibit high pressure drops, resulting in elevated energy consumption due to increased fan power requirements [26]. Moreover, they are ineffective against gaseous pollutants such as VOCs, SO_2 and NO_x , which can only be mitigated through complementary adsorption technologies (e.g., activated carbon or molecular sieves) [24].

In parallel, MERV-rated filters, typically ranging from MERV-1 to MERV-16, represent a broader class of air filters used in HVAC systems [27]. The MERV-13 filter, for example, is often adopted in GLAM environments and provides a balanced compromise between filtration efficiency and energy demand. It is capable of capturing higher or equal than 85% of particles between 1.0 and 3.0 μm , offering substantial protection against fine dust and biological agents, while maintaining a lower pressure drop compared to HEPA systems [24], [25], [28]. However, like HEPA filters, MERV-13 filters lack adsorption capacity for gaseous contaminants and their performance can be significantly affected by humidity and particulate loading over time.

Figure 2: Visual comparison of MERV-13 and HEPA filters. [21]

Both filtration systems require periodic maintenance and replacement, although their schedules differ depending on filter type and environmental conditions. MERV-13 filters generally need to be replaced every 3 to 6 months, offering a relatively low-maintenance and cost-effective option compatible with most HVAC systems [11]. HEPA filters, on the other hand, have more stringent maintenance requirements and typically require replacement every 6 to 12 months, as their high efficiency in trapping fine particles, viruses, and bacteria leads to faster clogging and pressure drop [11]. This periodic replacement generates solid waste streams that must be properly managed, often through land-filling or incineration and contributes to the overall environmental footprint of the filtration process. Additionally, filter manufacturing involves synthetic polymers, fibreglass and metallic frames, whose production and end-of-life disposal introduce further environmental burdens [29].

From a climate control perspective, air filtration is intrinsically connected to the energy performance of HVAC systems. The increase in air resistance induced by high-efficiency filters directly translates into higher energy use for air circulation. Studies have shown that filtration can account for up to 30-50% of the total energy demand of HVAC systems in museums and archives [29]. Consequently, improving indoor air quality without compromising energy efficiency represents one of the major engineering and sustainability challenges in the conservation of cultural heritage.

Recent research has focused on the integration of smart control systems and hybrid filtration technologies that combine mechanical and chemical adsorption processes [30]. However, despite these

advances, current commercial solutions are still limited in their ability to simultaneously address particulate and gaseous pollutants, while also maintaining low operational costs and environmental sustainability. This gap motivates the exploration of novel filtering materials, such as Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), which promise enhanced adsorption performance and potential for regeneration, as investigated in the SIMIACCI project (see Section 2.4).

2.4 The SIMIACCI project and MIL-100(Fe)

To overcome the limitations of existing air purification systems in cultural heritage environments, the SIMIACCI project (Sustainable Intelligent Management of Indoor Air Quality for the Culture and Creative Industries) was launched as a Europe initiative. Its main objective is to develop an integrated and sustainable framework for indoor air quality (IAQ) management specifically designed for GLAMs [1]. The project brings together research institutions, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and cultural organizations to co-create innovative technological solutions that combine advanced air filtration, real-time monitoring and energy-efficient management [1].

At the technological core of SIMIACCI is the use of Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs). Among them, MIL-100(Fe), composed of iron clusters and mesoporous cages, has been selected for its exceptional performance in adsorbing a wide range of indoor air pollutants under realistic conditions [6], [8]. A key feature contributing to the high adsorption performance of MIL-100(Fe) is its unique porous structure, which is composed of large mesoporous cages interconnected by microporous windows. This structure enables the selective trapping of a wide range of pollutant molecules while maintaining a high surface area.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the MIL-100(Fe) structure with the small S cage (left) and large L cage (right). [3]

As shown in Figure 3, MIL-100(Fe) consists of two types of cage: a smaller (S) cage and a larger (L) cage [6]. Both are constructed from iron(III) octahedra coordinated with trimeric acid linkers. This highly symmetrical framework allows for efficient molecular diffusion and adsorption, which is crucial for air purification applications in GLAM environments [6]. The open framework not only supports high pollutant capture but also facilitates regeneration processes via mild thermal or solvent treatment, thus reinforcing the material's potential for long-term, sustainable use in cultural heritage preservation [6].

According to the study by *Severino et al. (2025)*, the synthesis of MIL-100(Fe) can be optimised using two sustainable and scalable methods: solvent-free synthesis and microwave-assisted synthesis [6]. These approaches aim to improve the environmental sustainability and economic feasibility of producing this MOF on a large scale. The solvent-free synthesis method eliminates the use of organic solvents, reducing hazardous waste and associated disposal costs. This approach minimizes environmental impact and simplifies the purification process, leading to a more straightforward production pipeline. On the other hand, the microwave-assisted synthesis offers rapid heating and uniform temperature distribution, resulting in shorter reaction times and improved energy efficiency. It has been shown that this method can produce MIL-100(Fe) with high crystallinity and surface area, which are essential properties for effective pollutant adsorption. Despite these advancements, scaling up the production of MIL-100(Fe) presents challenges. Maintaining consistent quality, structural integrity and adsorption performance requires stringent control over precursor quality, reaction conditions and process parameters. Furthermore, economic considerations such as investment in synthesis reactors, raw materials, energy consumption and waste management infrastructure are critical factors that influence the feasibility of industrial-scale production [6].

Within this framework, SIMIACCI aims to integrate MIL-100(Fe) into compact, modular air purification systems specifically designed for GLAMs. These systems are characterized by low noise levels, minimal visual impact, and high pollutant selectivity, ensuring compatibility with the preservation requirements of cultural artefacts. To validate the proposed solutions, the project foresees the deployment of 20 prototype units across seven GLAM sites in Europe, engaging over 30,000 visitors in real operational environments [1]. Furthermore, the creation of the SIMIACCI label is intended to promote broader awareness and encourage adoption of these technologies within the cultural and creative sectors.

Within this context, the present thesis contributes to Work Package 11 (WP11) of the SIMIACCI project, which focuses on the environmental and social analyses. According to the project documentation, *“WP11 – Environmental and social analyses. D11.1 (IST ID, M42): Report on environmental analysis, social analysis and sustainability engagement plan. This deliverable is linked to tasks 11.2, 11.3 and 11.4 and aims to produce a comprehensive report on environmental analysis, social analysis, and the development of a sustainability engagement plan. Success will be measured by the creation of a detailed document that evaluates the environmental and social impacts of the SIMIACCI project, outlines stakeholder engagement strategies, and provides actionable recommendations for promoting sustainability throughout the project’s lifecycle”* [1].

Within this framework, the present thesis specifically addresses Task 11.2, focusing on the environmental assessment of MIL-100(Fe) production. A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is performed to quantify the environmental impacts associated with its industrial-scale synthesis using a gate-to-gate approach [9]. This includes all internal manufacturing stages, from raw material input to final product output, excluding upstream (resource extraction) and downstream (distribution, use and end-of-life) processes [9]. The objectives of this study are to identify environmental hotspots within the production

process, propose strategies for process optimization and provide quantitative data to support the validation of MOFs as sustainable air-purification materials for application in heritage environments.

Specifically, a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is performed to quantify the environmental impacts associated with its industrial-scale synthesis using a gate-to-gate approach. This includes all internal manufacturing stages, from raw material input to final product output, excluding upstream (resource extraction) and downstream (distribution, use and end-of-life) processes. The objectives of this study are to identify environmental hotspots within the production process, defined as the stages, inputs or outputs that contribute most significantly to the overall environmental impact, to propose strategies for process optimization and to provide quantitative data to support the validation of MOFs as sustainable air-purification materials for application in heritage environments.

In conclusion, this thesis aims to provide a comprehensive assessment of MIL-100(Fe)'s environmental footprint at industrial scale, offering insights that can guide sustainable production practises and support the integration of MOFs into next generation air filtration systems for cultural heritage preservation.

3 State of the art

The pursuit of sustainability within cultural heritage institutions has become an essential part of contemporary management and conservation strategies. As galleries, libraries, archives and museums strive to balance preservation requirements with environmental responsibility, new frameworks and technologies are being introduced to reduce energy consumption, minimize waste generation and improve indoor environmental quality. These institutions are not only custodians of cultural and historical artifacts but also complex operational systems that consume resources, generate emissions and interact with their surrounding environments.

In this context, sustainability must be understood as a multidimensional concept that encompasses environmental, social and economic aspects of institutional operation. Achieving sustainability in GLAMs involves integrating preventive conservation with low-impact technologies, developing energy-efficient HVAC systems and adopting innovative materials for air purification and climate control. This chapter provides a critical review of the state of the art concerning sustainability practices and environmental assessment methodologies in GLAMs. It begins with an overview of how sustainability has been conceptualized and implemented within these institutions (Section 3.1), followed by an analysis of the application LCA in GLAM environments and in air filtration systems (Section 3.2). The chapter concludes by identifying existing research gaps and outlining the scientific relevance of the present work (Section 3.3).

3.1 Sustainability concept in GLAM institutions

The concept of sustainability, widely recognized since the publication of the Brundtland Report in 1987 by the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development, is defined as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” [31]. Over time, this notion has evolved into a comprehensive framework encompassing three interdependent dimensions: environmental, social and economic, often referred to as the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) [32], [33], [34]. Within this framework, GLAM institutions have increasingly incorporated sustainability principles into their operations. As public cultural organizations, they have both an ethical and practical responsibility to reduce their environmental footprint while safeguarding cultural assets for future generations. Sustainability in GLAMs therefore extends beyond energy efficiency or waste management. It includes preventive conservation, responsible procurement, community engagement and long-term financial viability [35].

From the environmental perspective, sustainability in GLAM institutions focuses on minimizing emissions and resource use through the implementation of low-energy lighting, renewable energy sources and sustainable climate control systems. Many museums have undertaken initiatives to reduce their carbon footprint by optimizing HVAC performance and adopting adaptive climate management strategies. For example, the International Council of Museums (ICOM) has encouraged flexibility in environmental control standards to balance conservation needs with energy efficiency, particularly in

light of rising energy costs and climate targets [33], [34], [35]. While, from a social perspective, sustainability emphasizes inclusivity, accessibility and education. GLAMs play a key role in promoting public awareness of sustainability through exhibitions, outreach programs and sustainable cultural tourism. Finally, from an economic perspective, the sustainable management of cultural institutions focuses on the optimization of the usage of financial resources, lifecycle cost management and the development of partnerships that support sustainable innovation [33], [34].

In the last few years, an increasing number of studies have explored sustainability in museums, archives and libraries, addressing themes such as energy management, visitor behaviour, and the implementation of green building standards. However, this research remains fragmented, often focusing on single aspects rather than adopting a systemic approach that integrates environmental, social and economic perspective [33], [34].

Recently, the European Commission and the European Parliament have emphasized the importance of integrating sustainability principles into the cultural and creative sectors, as part of the broader objectives of the European Green Deal and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS) highlights that museums, libraries and archives play a dual role: preserving cultural heritage while reducing their environmental footprint and adapting to the challenges posed by climate change [36]. In line with this vision, several European initiatives promote the adoption of energy-efficient technologies, environmental monitoring and life cycle thinking within GLAM institutions. These programs encourage flexible climate control standards, preventive conservation strategies, and investment in energy-efficient HVAC systems, aligning preservation needs with the European's decarbonization goals [36].

Several ongoing European research projects, such as GoGreen, are also pioneering the development of green conservation practices and bio-based materials, as well as decision-making tools that integrate sustainability principles into preventive and remedial conservation [37]. These initiatives demonstrate how innovation and environmental responsibility can converge in heritage management, supporting the transition toward a sustainable cultural sector. In this context, sustainability is no longer an auxiliary goal but a structural dimension of heritage management. For institutions relying on controlled indoor environments, such as GLAMs, it directly intersects with IAQ and energy performance management. The integration of innovative materials for air purification, such as MOFs, illustrates how technological progress can bridge the gap between conservation objectives and environmental responsibility [6], [8], [36]. As sustainability principles become increasingly embedded within cultural institutions, the need for quantitative tools to measure environmental performance has grown. Among these, the LCA methodology has emerged as a key instrument for evaluating the environmental impacts of processes, materials and technologies applied in heritage conservation.

3.2 Life Cycle Assessment in GLAMs

In this project, the LCA methodology is applied to evaluate the environmental impacts of a system once its boundaries have been defined. While the previous section explored the conceptual framework of

sustainability and its relevance to GLAM institutions, this section investigates how LCA has been used in this context, based on a literature search conducted on *ScienceDirect*.

A search using the terms “GLAM” and “life cycle assessment” returned 26 results; however, most of these referred to GLAM as the acronym for “Global Guidance for Life Cycle Impact Assessment Indicators and Methods”, a framework developed within the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) for impact assessment methodologies. In other cases, the acronym stood for “General Large Area Model”, a designation commonly used in agricultural and environmental modelling. Although relevant to sustainability studies, these usages fall outside the scope of the present research, which focuses on cultural heritage institutions.

A subsequent search combining the terms “life cycle assessment”, “air filter”, and “museum” produced a single review article, “Sorption Direct Air Capture with CO₂ Utilization”, which addresses direct air capture technologies and their potential applications in carbon mitigation [38]. Although it includes a life cycle perspective and filtration processes, its focus is primarily on climate mitigation rather than cultural or museum applications. When the term “museum” was replaced with “galleries”, no results were found. However, substituting it with “library” yielded 14 results, of which seven were research articles. Among these, three were identified as particularly relevant to the present work.

The first article by *Yasin et al. (2024)* assesses the recycling of binary polymer carpets through LCA, quantifying the release of microplastics and revealing that the use phase contributes most significantly to the overall environmental impacts [39]. *Nandi et al. (2024)* examine the presence and composition of microplastics in indoor and outdoor air, demonstrating seasonal variability and their potential role as contaminant reservoirs in GLAM institutions, where air quality is critical for collection preservation [40]. Finally, *Mhuireach et al. (2021)* show that building materials significantly influence the emission of volatile organic compounds and the microbiological diversity of indoor air, underscoring the need for an integrated approach to environmental quality management in cultural spaces [41].

These studies collectively indicate that indoor air quality in cultural environments is affected by both particulate and chemical pollutants, as well as by the materials used in construction and furnishing [39], [40], [41]. However, there is a lack of research addressing the environmental impacts of air filtration systems themselves within GLAMs. The findings are particularly relevant for understanding the broader context of air quality management, although some works, such as that of *Yasin et al. (2024)*, are only indirectly related to air filtration processes, focusing instead on material recycling and microplastic release [39].

A further search combining “life cycle assessment” and “air filter” as keywords returned three relevant studies. *Rabello et al. (2024)* discuss the chemical recycling of PHBV-based air filters, where PHBV (poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)) is a biodegradable material recyclable through hydrolysis, thus reducing environmental impacts associated with the disposal of facial masks [42]. *Zhang et al. (2023)* review the development of transparent air filtration media, an essential innovation to improve communication during mask use [43]. *Agunda and Lateef (2022)* explore how nanotechnology can enhance antimicrobial air filters to combat harmful microorganisms and emerging pathogens [44].

These studies highlight significant advances in sustainable and functional filtration materials, focusing on biodegradability, transparency and antimicrobial properties [42], [43], [44]. Nevertheless, the environmental performance of these technologies at industrial scale remains largely unexplored, particularly in relation to their potential application in GLAM environments. The research is conceptually relevant as it demonstrates how material innovation can reduce environmental burdens and improve filtration efficiency, although its scope is mainly limited to personal protective equipment rather than to stationary air purification systems.

In addition, a search using “*museum*” and “*life cycle assessment*” as combined terms produced four results. *Campos et al. (2023)* examine the environmental impacts of tourism in a Spanish region using the LCA approach [45]. *Sanchez et al. (2023)* evaluate the environmental impacts of different anoxic treatments used for the preservation of artworks and historical artefacts [46]. *Menegaldo et al. (2023)* assess both the environmental and economic life cycle impacts of an innovative product: the *Novel Archive Box*, which applies nanotechnology for the preventive conservation of museum-stored artefacts [47]. The fourth article by *Bruhn et al. (2024)* is not directly related to museums, as it only references museum datasets in a historical carbon footprint analysis [48].

Overall, these studies demonstrate the versatility of LCA as a methodological framework for evaluating environmental impacts in the cultural heritage sector, encompassing tourism, conservation and material innovation. However, none of them address the environmental assessment of air filtration technologies within museums or archives. The studies by *Sanchez et al. (2023)* and *Menegaldo et al. (2023)* are particularly valuable as they provide insights into the sustainability of preventive conservation practices, while the work by *Bruhn et al. (2024)* offers only indirect contextual relevance [46], [47], [48].

Finally, a search with the terms “*library*” and “*life cycle assessment*”, and “*library*” as keyword, yielded 50 results. After filtering by subject areas such as Environmental Science, Chemical Engineering and Materials Science, 24 articles remained. However, none of them were directly related to the application of air filtration systems in GLAM institutions.

3.3 Literature on Metal-Organic Frameworks

In addition to the literature addressing Life Cycle Assessment applications within GLAMs, it is essential to explore studies focusing on Metal–Organic Frameworks (MOFs) and, more specifically, on MIL-100(Fe). This further analysis is motivated by the need to acquire a deeper understanding of the material’s intrinsic properties and, above all, of its synthesis pathways, which are crucial for the development of the present LCA study. In fact, the production process modelled in this thesis is based on the synthesis reported by *Severino et al. (2025)* [6], which represents one of the most comprehensive and industrially relevant studies currently available on MIL-100(Fe).

MOFs are a promising class of porous materials for environmental and industrial applications, due to their high surface area, tunable porosity and selective adsorption capacity. Among them, MIL-100(Fe) has gained significant attention for its structural robustness, chemical stability and the use of non-toxic iron centres [6].

Severino et al. (2021) [4] provide a comprehensive assessment of MOF industrialization, highlighting the limitations of traditional laboratory synthesis in terms of scalability, energy consumption and solvent use. The study identifies solvent recovery, energy demand and raw material purity as key cost drivers and suggested alternative approaches, such as solvent-free or microwave-assisted synthesis, which reduce both energy use and waste generation [4].

Further insights into the scalability of MOF production processes is offered by *Chen et al. (2024)*, who developed an aluminium-based microporous MOF optimized for post-combustion CO₂ capture [49]. Although the study does not specifically concern MIL-100(Fe), it provides valuable methodological insights regarding synthesis optimization, structural stability and cost–performance trade-offs under industrial conditions. The authors demonstrated that process intensification, through shorter reaction times, improved crystallinity, and reduced solvent use, can significantly reduce production costs without compromising adsorption efficiency [49]. These findings are transferable to iron-based MOF production.

Severino et al. (2025) [6] conducted a comprehensive techno-economic of MIL-100(Fe) synthesis, demonstrating that careful selection of the synthesis pathway can reduce production costs to below 30 USD/kg [6]. Two alternative routes were compared, employing iron sulphate and iron nitrate as metal precursors. A new optimized synthesis protocol was developed using iron sulphate under sustainable aqueous and ambient-pressure conditions in a 5 L laboratory pilot-scale reactor. This approach led to the formation of larger and more uniform particles, improved crystallinity and a substantially higher space–time yield. Drawing upon reliable pilot-scale data and established chemical engineering estimation methods, the authors showed that the optimized sulphate-based route significantly lowers production costs while maintaining high material quality [6].

These studies collectively highlight the potential of MIL-100(Fe) for environmentally benign synthesis and underscore the relevance of integrating LCA into process development, as optimization of synthesis parameters directly impacts both the material's environmental and economic performance.

The present thesis builds upon the synthesis data reported by *Severino et al. (2025)* to apply LCA to the industrial production of MIL-100(Fe), providing the first comprehensive quantification of its environmental footprint in the context of sustainable air purification technologies for cultural heritage environments.

3.4 Research gaps

The literature review reveals a significant gap in the application of LCA to cultural heritage institutions, particularly within the GLAM sector. Despite the growing relevance of sustainability in museums, libraries and archives, the majority of studies focus on energy management, preventive conservation or the characterization of pollutants, while the systematic evaluation of environmental impacts through LCA remains limited.

The bibliometric search conducted on *ScienceDirect* confirms this lack of research, since most publications that combine the terms “GLAM” and “life cycle assessment” refer not to cultural institutions but to methodological frameworks for environmental modelling. Even when extending the search to related terms such as “museum,” “library” or “air filter,” the number of studies directly linking LCA to heritage conservation remains extremely low. Only a few papers apply LCA to specific conservation processes, such as anoxic treatments, nanotechnology-based materials or recycling of polymer-based components, but none address indoor air management or filtration systems within GLAM environments.

This absence of research is critical because air quality control represents one of the main contributors to energy consumption and environmental impact in heritage buildings. HVAC systems and air filters, essential for preventive conservation, often have high operational and end-of-life burdens, yet their life cycle performance has rarely been quantified. As a result, decision-makers lack the necessary data to assess trade-offs between preservation efficiency and environmental sustainability.

Furthermore, no studies to date have evaluated the environmental performance of innovative filtration materials, such as MOFs, in the context of cultural heritage. Although studies such as *Severino et al. (2025)* [6] provide detailed techno-economic data and optimized synthesis routes for MIL-100(Fe), their environmental implications at industrial scale remain largely unexplored. Existing literature on MOF synthesis highlights key cost drivers, potential process optimizations, and scalable production strategies, but none integrate these findings within a full LCA framework. Consequently, gaps remain in understanding how the choice of synthetic route, precursor materials, reactor scale and crystallinity control affect not only production efficiency and cost but also the environmental footprint of the material.

Therefore, there is a clear need for comprehensive LCA studies that assess the environmental impacts associated with air filtration technologies used in GLAMs, including innovative materials such as MIL-100(Fe). Such studies would enable the identification of environmental hotspots, support the optimization of production and operational processes and provide a scientific basis for the sustainable management of indoor environments in cultural heritage institutions. The present thesis aims to address this gap by applying LCA to the production of MIL-100(Fe), thereby providing the first complete quantification of its environmental footprint in the context of sustainable air purification within the SIMIACCI project framework.

4 Methodology

The research methodology employed in this thesis is based on the ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards, which establish the principles, framework and requirements for conducting a Life Cycle Assessment [9], [10]. According to these guidelines, the LCA approach is structured into four key steps:

1. Goal and Scope definition

This initial phase lays the foundation of the study by defining its primary objectives, specifying the product system under investigation, the functional unit and establishing the system boundaries. It also sets out the assumptions, limitations and intended applications of the results, ensuring the transparency and reproducibility of the LCA. Moreover, this phase includes the identification of the target audience and the intended mode of communication of the outcomes.

In this thesis, the Goal and Scope Definition phase establishes the methodological foundation for assessing the environmental performance of scaled-up production process of MIL-100(Fe), an iron-based MOF with potential applications in air purification. This phase is described in detail in Section 4.1.

2. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) analysis

This phase involves the systematic collection and calculation of quantitative data describing all relevant input and output flows associated with the processes included within the defined system boundaries. These flows include the consumption of material, energy, water and the generation of emissions, product and waste throughout the system under study.

The main objective of the LCI is to establish a comprehensive and transparent mass and energy balance for the considered system, ensuring that all relevant exchanges between the technosphere and the environment are represented accurately. Data sources may include primary data, directly measured or experimentally obtained from laboratory or pilot-scale operations, and secondary data, retrieved from databases, literature or industry reports. This combination ensures both representativeness and completeness of the inventory.

In this thesis, the LCI quantifies all material and energy exchanges involved in the scaled-up production process of MIL-100(Fe), integrating primary data from laboratory and pilot-scale synthesis reported by *Severino et al., 2025* [6] with secondary data from the Ecoinvent v3.9.1 database. The data were modelled and processed in SimaPro v9.6.0.1.

A detailed description of the data sources, modelling assumptions, and the resulting mass and energy balances is provided in Section 4.2.

3. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The third step translates the inventory data into potential environmental impacts through classification and characterization models. The Impact Assessment phase quantifies how the input and output flows identified in the inventory, such as energy use, emissions and material

consumption, contribute to specific environmental issues. This step is structured into four main stages: classification, characterisation, normalisation and weighting.

During **classification**, each input and output from the inventory is assigned to one or more impact categories (e.g., *Climate change*, *Acidification*, *Eutrophication*), according to the selected impact assessment method. In the **characterisation** phase, each flow is multiplied by a specific characterisation factor, which quantifies its potential contribution to the relevant environmental impact. The result of this step is a set of characterised impact values, expressed in distinct physical units (e.g., kg CO₂ eq, mol H⁺ eq), representing the potential environmental burdens associated with the system.

Since the impact categories use different units, direct comparison among them is not possible until normalisation and weighting are applied. Normalisation converts the characterised results into dimensionless values by dividing them by reference normalisation factors, allowing results to be compared across different impact categories and providing an understanding of their relative magnitude. Weighting assigns a relative importance to each category and can aggregate them into a Single Score (SS), representing the total environmental burden of the analysed system.

In this thesis, for the Impact Assessment, the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 adapted method is applied using SimaPro v9.6.0.1. This method was selected to ensure consistency with the most recent European guidelines and to enable comparability with other LCA studies on advanced materials. The EF method allows evaluation across multiple environmental categories, including *Climate change*, *Resource use*, *Eutrophication*, *Ecotoxicity*, among others.

This phase is described in detail in Section 4.3, where the impact categories included in the EF 3.1 method are reported and discussed.

4. Interpretation

The final step focuses on analysing the results obtained from the previous stage, identifying the most significant contributions to environmental impacts, and formulating improvement strategies to enhance the overall sustainability of the production process of MIL-100(Fe).

This final stage is generally discussed in Section 4.4 and further expanded in Chapter 5 (Results and Discussion), where the results are critically analysed, including a comparative assessment of the environmental impact between MIL-100(Fe) and the materials used in traditional filters commonly employed in GLAM environments, namely HEPA (glass fibre) and MERV-13 (polypropylene granulate).

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the four main phases of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework, according to ISO 14040 and ISO 14044.

The following sections provide a detailed description of how each phase has been implemented in the case study of MIL-100(Fe) production.

4.1 Goal and Scope definition

This section outlines the first phase of LCA, provides the foundation for the entire study and ensure methodological consistency. According to ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, it defines the study's objectives, the product system under investigation, the functional unit and the system boundaries, while also clarifying the assumptions, limitations and intended applications of the results. These elements are fundamental to ensure transparency, reproducibility and comparability throughout the assessment process.

4.1.1 Goal of the study

The main objective of this study is to assess the environmental impacts of an industrial-scale production process of MIL-100(Fe). By applying the LCA methodology, the study aims to identify the main environmental hotspots along the production process and to provide recommendations for the improvement of the process from an environmental sustainability perspective. Beyond its diagnostic function, this assessment contributes to the ongoing research on sustainable metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) and aims to generate knowledge relevant for both academic and industrial contexts, particularly in relation to advanced sorbents for air purification and environmental remediation.

The results are intended to inform academic research on sustainable materials, while also providing industry with a data-driven basis for decision-making regarding the scaling-up of MOF production. They also include a comparative analysis between the environmental impact of MIL-100(Fe) production and that of the materials used in traditional filters commonly employed in GLAMs, namely glass fibres for HEPA filters and polypropylene granulate for MERV-13 filters. Specifically, the findings are expected to highlight the environmental trade-offs of the MIL-100(Fe) production process and to serve as guidance for the development of more sustainable sorbent-based filtration technologies.

The primary audience of this work comprises academic researchers in chemical engineering and materials science, as well as industrial stakeholders considering the industrialisation of MIL-100(Fe) and similar MOFs.

4.1.2 System definition

The system investigated in this study is the industrial-scale synthesis of MIL-100(Fe), a MOF with promising applications in environmental remediation and air purification. Among the two alternative synthesis routes proposed by *Severino et al. (2025)* and reported in Figure 5, one nitrate-based and one sulphate-based, this study focuses exclusively on the sulphate-based route, which has demonstrated high space-time yield (STY), better scalability and high product purity under mild reaction conditions [6].

Figure 5: a) Simplified block diagram of the large-scale production process of MIL-100(Fe)-S-5L. Effluents in grey, inputs in purple and outputs in blue. b) Simplified block diagram of the large-scale process developed for production cost calculations of MIL-100(Fe)-N-5L. Effluents in green, inputs in purple, important energy inputs in red and outputs in blue. [6]

4.1.3 Functional unit

The functional unit chosen is 1 kton/year of MIL-100(Fe) in dry powder form, stored and ready for either application or distribution. This unit provides a clear and consistent basis for the normalisation of input and output flows and enables comparison with other MOFs production processes in future studies. Selecting an annualised mass-based functional unit also reflects the typical planning and production metrics used in industrial-scale manufacturing. This ensures alignment between environmental analysis and production planning.

4.1.4 System boundaries

The system boundaries define which processes will be included in the LCA study and they are essential to ensure the consistency and comparability of the results obtained in the LCA. These boundaries are defined in three distinct dimensions: physical, geographical and temporal.

In this study, a gate-to-gate physical boundary has been selected. This approach restricts the analysis to the core production stages directly associated with the synthesis of MIL-100(Fe), starting from the input of raw chemical precursors to the final storage of the dry MOF powder. This system boundary excludes both upstream processes, such as the extraction and production of sodium hydroxide, benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylate acid (BTC) and iron(III) salts, and downstream stages, such as transportation, product packaging, use phase or end-of-life treatment. These physical boundaries are suitable for identifying environmental impacts strictly related to the production process and for supporting process improvement efforts. The main unit operations included within these system boundaries are as follow:

- Reaction of BTC and iron(III) salts in aqueous solution with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) at room temperature (25°C);
- Filtration of the resulting slurry to separate the solid product from unreacted reagents and byproducts (e.g. sodium salts, sulphates);
- Drying to remove residual moisture and obtain a dry solid product;
- Milling to ensure a uniform powder, characterised by particle homogeneity and suitable morphology;
- Storage of the final MIL-100(Fe) powder for subsequent use or distribution.

These steps correspond to the industrial pathway proposed by *Severino et al. (2025)* and reported in Figure 5 (a), which is designed to achieve high yields of MIL-100(Fe) under mild and scalable reaction conditions [6].

The geographical boundaries refer to the location where the processes included in the system are assumed to occur. In this study, the production of MIL-100(Fe) is modelled to take place in Europe, consistently with the industrial context foreseen by the European project SIMIACCI, to which this thesis contributes. Accordingly, during the modelling performed in SimaPro, background data were primarily sourced from Ecoinvent v3.9 datasets referring to the “Europe without Switzerland” or “Europe (RER)” region; when these datasets were unavailable, equivalent European datasets were used instead. This assumption reflects the intended industrial context for the material’s development and aligns with the regional representativeness of the selected datasets.

The temporal boundary defines the period considered in the analysis. Given that the functional unit is based on an annual production rate (1 kton per year), the temporal boundary of the system corresponds

to a one-year operational cycle of industrial production. This assumption provides a consistent reference frame for normalising material and energy flows and allows comparison with other LCA studies conducted on an annual basis.

4.2 Life Cycle Inventory Analysis

The second phase of the LCA is the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) which comprises the quantification and compilation of all inputs and outputs related to the flows inside the product system through its entire life cycle or with the system boundaries.

4.2.1 Inventory building in SimaPro

The data processing and system modelling were performed using the LCA software SimaPro (v9.6.0.1) [50]. The background data were sourced from the Ecoinvent v3.9.1 database [51], employing the “cut-off, U” system model.

This attributional model considers only the direct environmental burdens of primary production, assuming that recycled materials or by-products leave the system without credits to the generating process. The “U” refers to unit process, which provides disaggregated datasets, allowing greater transparency and flexibility in integrating primary laboratory and pilot-scale data with secondary data from the database. In contrast, the “cut-off, S” model (system process) offers aggregated data that are easier to handle but less transparent and not editable. The “cut-off, U” model was therefore selected for this study to ensure methodological transparency and full compatibility with the LCA approach, the gate-to-gate system boundaries and the EF 3.1 impact assessment method applied.

All flows introduced in SimaPro as materials, fuels and emissions were modelled using secondary data from Ecoinvent, considered suitable to represent the main inputs and outputs of the scaled-up synthesis of MIL-100(Fe). The datasets were selected as “market for” processes, representing the average market supply of materials within the European region under the cut-off allocation model. This approach guarantees methodological consistency and transparency in data sourcing.

For certain substances, however, no corresponding flow was available in the Ecoinvent database. In these cases, new elementary flows were created ad hoc to ensure a complete inventory representation. This was necessary for benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylate (BTC), which is not included in Ecoinvent. Instead of using a proxy such as terephthalic acid, a dedicated process was developed to represent BTC production, based on stoichiometric synthesis reactions and industrially relevant operating conditions (further detailed in Section 4.2.4). For all other input materials and utilities, existing Ecoinvent datasets were employed.

4.2.2 Data collection

Before proceeding with system modelling in SimaPro, it was necessary to collect and process the experimental data related to the synthesis of MIL-100(Fe). The primary reference for this study is *Severino et al. (2025)* [6], which reports the pilot-scale synthesis of the material under mild aqueous conditions. Based on the information provided in that work, the reaction leading to the formation of MIL-100(Fe), whose empirical formula is $[\text{Fe}_3\text{O}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{CO}_2)_3)_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, was reconstructed starting from iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and 1,3,5-benzene-tricarboxylic acid (BTC), as the main precursors, both dissolved in deionized water [6]. The empirical formula of BTC corresponds to $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{O}_6$,

Considering the molecular weights of the compounds involved in Reaction (1) and the corresponding molar material balance derived from its stoichiometry, the material balance (MB) was subsequently determined in mass terms. These data are summarized in Table 1, assuming complete conversion of the reagents, i.e., a 100% yield.

Table 1: Material balance in molar and mass basis based on the stoichiometry of chemical reaction (1), considering a 100% yield.

Compound	MW [g/mol]	MB in molar terms		MB in mass basis	
		IN [-]	OUT [-]	IN [g]	OUT [g]
$\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	278.01	3	0	834.03	0
BTC	210.14	2	0	420.28	0
H_2O	18.02	0	19	0	342.29
H^+	1.01	0	6	0	6.05
O^{2-}	15.99	1	0	15.99	0
OH	17.00	1	0	17.01	0
SO_4^{2-}	96.06	0	3	0	288.19
MIL-100(Fe)	650.85	0	1	0	650.85
Total		/	/	1287.32	1287.38

The small discrepancy between input and output masses (0.07 g) is due to rounding of molecular weights and is negligible (< 0.005%).

The stoichiometric data were then adapted starting from the experimental data given by *Severino et al. 2025* [6]. Since the amount of iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate used in the pilot experiment is equal to 315.5 g, the quantities of all other compounds involved in Reaction (1) were calculated by applying a scaling factor (rate). This factor corresponds to the ratio between the experimental amount of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicated by *Severino et al. (2025)* [6] and the stoichiometric amount of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reported in Table 1. Its expression is reported in Equation (2).

$$\text{rate} = \frac{m_{\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{exp}}}{m_{\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}, \text{theor}}} = 0.38 [-] \quad (2)$$

By applying this rate proportionally to all reactants and products, the scaled mass balance of the reaction (1) was determined again assuming a 100% yield and reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Data scaled according to the amount of iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate used in the pilot-scale synthesis (considering yield = 100%).

Compound	IN [g]	OUT [g]
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	315.5	0
BTC	158.99	0
H ₂ O	0	129.48
H ⁺	0	2.29
O ⁻²	6.05	0
OH	6.43	0
SO ₄ ⁻²	0	109.02
MIL-100(Fe)	0	246.21
Total	486.97	486.99

Similarly to the previous balance, a slight discrepancy is observed between the total input mass and the total output mass, which is attributed to rounding errors and considered acceptable within the uncertainty limits of the calculations. Also in this case, the mass balance error is lower than 0.005%.

Subsequently, the amount of BTC reported in *Severino et al. (2025)* [6], equal to 162.4 g, was also considered. A new mass balance for Reaction (1) was then calculated, this time considering the experimental yield of 93% reported by the authors [6].

For the unreacted portion of the iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate, the output mass was calculated according to Equation (3).

$$m_{FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O}^{OUT} = m_{FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O}^{IN} \cdot (1 - Y) \quad (3)$$

Similarly, the output BTC accounts for the unreacted fraction is obtained through Equation (4).

$$m_{BTC}^{OUT} = m_{BTC}^{IN} - m_{BTC}^{IN}(Y = 100\%) + m_{BTC}^{IN}(Y = 100\%) \cdot (1 - Y) \quad (4)$$

For the reaction products, i.e. water (H₂O), protons (H⁺), sulphate ions (SO₄²⁻) and the final product MIL-100(Fe), the output mass was determined using Equation (5).

$$m_i^{OUT} = m_i^{OUT}(Y = 100\%) \cdot Y \quad (5)$$

Finally, for oxygen (O⁻²) and hydroxide ions (OH⁻), the same approach as for iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate was applied. Their input mass was kept the same as those shown in Table 2, while the output masses were adjusted according to Equation (6).

$$m_i^{OUT} = m_i^{IN} \cdot (1 - Y) \quad (6)$$

These mathematical relationships were used to compute the material balance that forms the basis for the subsequent scaling to the functional unit defined in Section 4.1. This balance accounts for both the amount of iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate and the quantity of BTC specified in the reference paper. It should be noted that the BTC quantity in this mass balance is slightly higher than the stoichiometric requirement, in accordance with the experimental procedure reported by *Severino et al. (2025)* [6]. The final data obtained are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Data scaled according to the amount of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and BTC used in the pilot-scale synthesis (yield = 93%).

Compound	IN [g]	OUT [g]
$\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	315.5	22.085
BTC	162.4	14.54
H_2O	0	120.42
H^+	0	2.13
O^{2-}	6.05	0.42
OH	6.43	0.45
SO_4^{2-}	0	101.39
MIL-100(Fe)	0	228.97
Total	490.39	490.41

The slight discrepancy between total input and output masses (less than 0.005%) arises from rounding errors in molecular weights and numerical approximations. Such a deviation is considered negligible and falls within the acceptable tolerance range for LCA modelling and mass balance closure.

To obtain data consistent with the functional unit (FU) of 1 kton per year of MIL-100(Fe) in dry powder form, all mass flows were proportionally scaled to the target production level. The resulting input and output flows, expressed in mass terms, are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Input and output flows for production of 1 kton/year of MIL-100(Fe).

Compound	IN [kg]	OUT [kg]
$\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1377892.95	96452.51
BTC	709254.57	63516.93
H_2O	0	525910.52
H^+	0	9296.93
O^{2-}	26433.45	1850.27
OH	28098.75	1966.90
SO_4^{2-}	0	442786.28
MIL-100(Fe)	0	1000000
Total	2141679.72	2141780.34

The resulting mass balance error is equal to 100.62 Kg corresponding to a relative error of 0.0047%. Such a deviation is negligible and considered acceptable for LCA purposes, being solely due to rounding in molecular weights and scaling factors.

The resulting dataset presented in Table 4 represents the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) for the reaction step of MIL-100(Fe) synthesis. The corresponding mass flows were subsequently implemented in SimaPro

and modelled using background data from Ecoinvent, in accordance with the assumptions outlined in Section 4.1. This dataset provides the quantitative foundation for the environmental modelling of the process. The detailed mass and energy balances for each unit operation within the production system are presented and discussed in Section 4.2.3.

4.2.3 Material and utilities balances

This section reports the mass and energy balances for all the unit operations included in the system boundaries. These balances represent the quantitative basis for the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) and were developed using both secondary data, reported in Table A.1 in Appendix A, and engineering assumptions.

The mass balance for the reaction step was derived from the stoichiometric and yield-based calculations presented in Section 4.2.2 (Table 4). To this dataset, additional inputs related to electricity demand and process water consumption were incorporated to provide a complete representation of the material and utility flows. The complete tables used to derive these values are provided in Table A.1 in Appendix A.

To explain how these data were determined, the following paragraphs summarize the key assumptions and computational steps used for estimating the electricity, process water and steam requirements across all process steps: reaction, filtration, drying, milling and storage.

Electricity

Electricity consumption was obtained from the reference Excel dataset for both the reaction and milling units. The data were initially provided in watt-hours (Wh) and then converted to kilowatt-hours per year (kWh/year) according to the production capacity associated with the functional unit. It is important to note that no electricity recovery occurs in the system; therefore, all electrical energy is considered as an input, with no corresponding output flow.

Table 5: Electricity data.

	Reactor	Mill
Electricity	5172675 Wh	8266 Wh
	5172.67 kWh	8.27 kWh
	41588310.02 kWh/year	66456.40 kWh/year

Vapour

Steam is used exclusively in the drying step to supply the thermal energy required for moisture removal. The base data obtained from the Excel file correspond to a steam flow rate of 3423 kg/h. This value was converted into kg/year by considering the annual operating time of the system, which is equal to 8040 h. Since steam is fully condensed during drying, the input and output mass flows are assumed equal.

Table 6: Vapour data.

Vapour	Dryer	
		3423
	27520474.77	kg/year

Process water

Process water is used primarily in the reaction and filtration steps. The initial data were obtained from the Excel file, expressed as total mass per batch (kg). These values were converted to kg/h considering a reaction time of 48 h, as reported by *Severino et al., 2025* [6], and subsequently normalized to kg/year for inclusion in the LCI.

Most of the process water entering the reactor exits the system during filtration. Hence, it was assumed that the total process water input in the reactor is fully recovered in the subsequent step. During filtration, it was assumed that the filter cake retains 30% moisture, which is entirely removed in the drying stage. The amount of water evaporated during drying was therefore modelled as equal to the moisture content entering the dryer.

Table 7: Process water data.

Process water	Reactor		Filter	
		254588	kg	44776
	5303.91	kg/h	932.84	kg/h
	42643447.7	kg/year	7500000	kg/year

It is possible to notice that the storage step does not involve any significant mass or energy exchanges other than the input and output of the same amount of MIL-100(Fe) powder. Therefore, it was modelled as a static process unit, without additional flows.

The final material and utility balances, normalized to the functional unit (1 kton/year of MIL-100(Fe)), are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8: Final dataset derived from literature-based secondary data.

REACTOR				
Material/Utilities	Inputs		Outputs	
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1377892.95	kg	96452.51	kg
BTC	709254.57	kg	63516.93	kg
H ₂ O	0	kg	525910.52	kg
H ⁺	0	kg	9296.93	kg
O ⁻²	26433.45	kg	1850.27	kg
OH	28098.75	kg	1966.90	kg
SO ₄ ⁻²	0	kg	442786.28	kg
MIL-100(Fe)	0	kg	1000000	kg
Electricity	41588.31	kWh/year	0	kWh/year
Process water	42643447.7	kg	42643447.7	kg
FILTRATION				
Material/Utilities	Inputs		Outputs	
MIL-100(Fe)	1000000	kg	1000000	kg
Process water	7500000	kg	7200000	kg
DRYING				
Material/Utilities	Inputs		Outputs	
MIL-100(Fe)	1000000	kg	1000000	kg
Process water	300000	kg	300000	kg
Vapour	27520474.77	kg	27520474.77	kg
MILLING				
Material/Utilities	Inputs		Outputs	
MIL-100(Fe)	1000000	kg	1000000	kg
Electricity	66456.40135	kWh/year	0	kWh/year
STORAGE				
Material/Utilities	Inputs		Outputs	
MIL-100(Fe)	1000000	kg	1000000	kg

The electricity represents the main energy input during the reaction and milling stages, while in the drying stage the primary energy source is steam, which enables the material dehydration process. Process water dominates the mass flows, reflecting the aqueous nature of the synthesis and aligning with the experimental data reported by *Severino et al. (2025)* [6].

4.2.4 Modelling in SimaPro

The process modelling was performed in SimaPro. Each unit operation involved in the production of MIL-100(Fe) was modelled as a separate process, in accordance with the *one process per unit operation* principle. The five processes (reaction, filtration, drying, milling, and storage) were then interconnected sequentially, following the production pathway illustrated in Figure 5, Section 4.1.2.

The quantitative data entered into SimaPro were derived from the material and energy balances presented in Section 4.2.3, while the selection of flow types from the Ecoinvent database was based on the geographical boundaries defined in Section 4.1.4.

Reaction Step

The quantitative input and output data for the reaction phase were primarily taken from the material balances developed in Section 4.2.3. However, several flows were further refined to properly reflect the actual substances included in the Ecoinvent database.

- **Iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate (FeSO₄·7H₂O)**

In the material balance, iron(II) sulphate heptahydrate (FeSO₄·7H₂O) was reported as a single substance. However, in SimaPro, this compound was represented by two separate flows: iron(II) sulphate (FeSO₄) and water (H₂O), based on the hydration Reaction (7).

Given the total amount of hydrated salt required for the process (1,377,892.95 kg), the corresponding masses of FeSO₄ and H₂O were calculated by converting the total mass into moles, using the molecular weights and applying the stoichiometric ratios (Table 9).

Table 9: Input amounts of iron (II) sulphate and water.

	MW		mass			moles		
FeSO4	151.91	g/mol	752889119.7	g	752889.12	kg	4956217.71	mol
H2O	18.02	g/mol	625003834.1	g	625003.83	kg	34693523.96	mol
FeSO4•7H2O	278.01	g/mol	1377892954	g	1377892.95	kg	4956217.71	mol

Using the same approach, the amount of FeSO₄ and H₂O leaving the reaction step was calculated based on the total output of FeSO₄·7H₂O reported in Table 8. These data are reported in Table (10).

Table 10: Output data if iron(II) sulphate and water.

	MW		mass			moles		
FeSO4	151.91	g/mol	52702238.38	g	52702.24	kg	346935.24	mol
H2O	18.02	g/mol	43750268.39	g	43750.27	kg	2428546.68	mol
FeSO4•7H2O	278.01	g/mol	96452506.77	g	96452.51	kg	346935.24	mol

Water leaving the system is expressed in kilograms but in SimaPro it must be expressed in cubic meters; thus, 43.75 m³ of water were set. The total water output also includes 525,910.52 kg of process water from Table 8 (Section 4.2.3), resulting in a combined total reported in Table 17.

- **1,3,5-Benzenetricarboxylic acid (BTC)**

The compound BTC (C₉H₆O₆) was not available in the Ecoinvent database. Therefore, a dedicated production pathway was modelled, reconstructing its synthesis through three intermediate reactions:

1. Formation of chloromethane (CH₃Cl)

Methanol (CH₃OH) reacts with hydrogen chloride (HCl) to form chloromethane and water, according to the Reaction (8).

2. Formation of trimethylbenzene (C₉H₁₂)

Benzene (C₆H₆) reacts with three moles of chloromethane to form 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene (C₉H₁₂) and hydrogen chloride as expressed in Reaction (9).

3. Oxidation of trimethylbenzene to BTC

Trimethylbenzene reacts with oxygen to produce BTC and water, according to Reaction (10).

The corresponding mass and molar quantities for each reaction were calculated to obtain 1 kg of the target product (CH₃Cl, C₉H₁₂ and BTC respectively) and they are reported in Table 11-13.

Table 11: Reaction (8): Production of chloromethane.

	MW		mass		moles			
CH3OH	32.04	g/mol	634.71	g	0.63	kg	19.81	mol
HCl	36.46	g/mol	722.27	g	0.72	kg	19.81	mol
CH3Cl	50.48	g/mol	1000	g	1	kg	19.81	mol
H2O	18.02	g/mol	356.97	g	0.357	kg	19.81	mol

Water output is expressed in kilograms but in SimaPro must be converted in cubic meters. So, it results into 3.57·10⁻⁴ m³.

Table 12: Reaction (9): Production of 1,3,5-trimethylbenzene (C₉H₁₂).

	MW		mass		moles			
C6H6	78.11	g/mol	649.89	g	0.65	kg	8.32	mol
CH3Cl	50.48	g/mol	1260.00	g	1.26	kg	24.96	mol
C9H12	120.19	g/mol	1000	g	1	kg	8.32	mol
HCl	36.46	g/mol	910.06	g	0.91	kg	24.96	mol

Table 13: Reaction (10): Production of BTC.

	MW	mass		moles
C9H12	120.19 g/mol	571.95 g	0.57 kg	4.76 mol
O2	31.99 g/mol	685.24 g	0.69 kg	21.42 mol
C9H6O6	210.13 g/mol	1000 g	1 kg	4.76 mol
H2O	18.02 g/mol	257.20 g	0.257 kg	14.28 mol

Water output in SimaPro is equal to $2.57 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ m}^3$.

Both the input and output BTC flows used in the reaction step correspond to the quantities calculated in the material balance for the production of 1 kton of MIL-100(Fe) per year, which represents the selected functional unit. These quantities are reported in Table 8, Section 4.2.3.

- **Sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄)**

Hydrogen ions (H⁺) and sulphate ions (SO₄²⁻) generated during the synthesis were combined into a single output flow corresponding to sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄), according to the stoichiometric relation (11).

Table 14: Output data for sulfuric acid.

	MW	mass		moles
H+	1.00 g/mol	9296930.88 g	9296.93 kg	9223145.71 mol
SO4	96.06 g/mol	442786279.9 g	442786.28 kg	4609476.16 mol
H2SO4	98.08 g/mol	452078983.8 g	452078.98 kg	4609476.16 mol

- **Sodium hydroxide (NaOH)**

The hydroxide ions (OH⁻) entering the system are supplied as sodium hydroxide (NaOH), as indicated by *Severino et al. (2025)* [6]. The dissociation of NaOH can be expressed as reported in Reaction (12).

Table 15: Data related to sodium hydroxide input.

	MW	mass		moles
NaOH	39.99 g/mol	66080311.7 g	66080.31 kg	1652090.40 mol
Na	22.99 g/mol	37981558.23 g	37981.56 kg	1652090.40 mol
OH	17.01 g/mol	28098753.47 g	28098.75 kg	1652090.40 mol

Similarly, the NaOH output and residual sodium ions (Na⁺) in the aqueous phase were determined from stoichiometric considerations. The residual amount of Na⁺ leaving the reaction corresponds to the difference between the Na⁺ input (Table 15) and the output (Table 16), resulting in 35,322,864.79 kg, which corresponds to 35,322.87 m³ of water, assuming a density of 1000 kg/m³.

Table 16: Data used for modelling the output of sodium hydroxide and sodium ions.

	MW		mass			moles	
NaOH	39.99	g/mol	4625594.62	g	4625.59	kg	115645.65 mol
Na	22.99	g/mol	2658693.44	g	2658.69	kg	115645.65 mol
OH	17.01	g/mol	1966901.18	g	1966.90	kg	115645.65 mol

All the input and output flows associated with the reaction step are summarized in Table 17, while the complete dataset implemented in SimaPro is provided in Appendix B Table B.1. It is possible to observe that in Table 17, all process outputs are represented using the generic “wastewater, average” flow from Ecoinvent, since the use of specific chemical datasets (or the custom flow created for BTC) resulted in inconsistencies during the impact category calculation phase of the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA).

Table 17: Inventory input and output data used for modelling the reaction step.

Reaction			
Materials/fuels	Value	Units	Data source
FeSO ₄	752889.10	kg	Calculated data
Water of hydration	625003.80	kg	Calculated data
BTC	709254.60	kg	Calculated data
Oxygen	26433.45	kg	Calculated data
Sodium hydroxide	66080.31	kg	Calculated data
Process water	42643448	kg	Calculated data
Electricity/heat			
Electricity	41588310	kWh	Calculated data
Emissions to air			
Oxygen	1850.27	kg	Calculated data
Waste to treatment			
Water	569.66	m ³	Calculated data
BTC	63.52	m ³	Calculated data
Process water	42643.45	m ³	Calculated data
Sulfuric acid	452.08	m ³	Calculated data
Iron sulphate	52.70	m ³	Calculated data
Sodium hydroxide	66.08	m ³	Calculated data
Sodium	35.32	m ³	Calculated data

Filtration, Drying, Milling and Storage

For the process steps following the reaction stage, i.e. filtration, drying, milling and storage, the quantitative data implemented in SimaPro were directly taken from the mass and energy balances reported in Section 4.2.3. The only adjustments applied concerned the conversion of the water output quantities into cubic meters (m³) and the transformation of the steam flow entering (and equivalently leaving) the drying unit into megajoules (MJ). To correctly model this energy flow in SimaPro, the steam mass was converted into energy units using the specific enthalpy of saturated steam (Δh_v) at approximately 150°C, which corresponds to the process temperature described by *Severino et al.* (2025). The conversion was performed according to the Equation (8).

$$E_{\text{steam}} = \dot{m}_{\text{steam}} \times \Delta h_v \quad (8)$$

Where:

- E_{steam} = total energy associated with steam [MJ/year]
- \dot{m}_{steam} = annual steam mass flow [kg/year]
- Δh_v = specific enthalpy of saturated steam [kJ/kg]

The inventory data for the filtration, drying, milling and storage steps are summarized in Table 18, while the complete dataset implemented in SimaPro is provided in Appendix B (Table B.2).

Table 18: Inventory input and output data used for modelling the filtration, drying and milling step of the production process of MIL-100(Fe).

Filtration			
Materials/fuels	Value	Units	Data source
Water	7500000	kg	Calculated data
Waste to treatment			
Water	7200	m ³	Calculated data
Drying			
Materials/fuels	Value	Units	Data source
Water	300000	kg	Calculated data
Heat	75569297	MJ	Calculated data
Waste to treatment			
Water	300	m ³	Calculated data
Milling			
Electricity	Value	Units	Data source
Electricity	66456.40	kWh	Calculated data

4.2.5 Modelling of the comparative production processes in SimaPro

It was also necessary to model the production processes of the materials that constitute traditional filters commonly used in GLAM environments, namely glass fibre (for HEPA filters) and polypropylene granulate (for MERV-13 filters). This modelling step was essential to enable a consistent comparison between the production process of these materials and that of MIL-100(Fe), which is the main focus of this study. Both processes are already available in the Ecoinvent v3.9.1 database and the selected datasets are reported in Table 19.

For the comparison, it was necessary to define the amount of material to be modelled. Although the filtration capacity of traditional filters (HEPA and MERV-13) is well documented in the literature [3], that of MIL-100(Fe) has not yet been experimentally determined. Therefore, the comparison was performed by considering the production of the same amount of material, corresponding to 1 kton/year, which is consistent with the functional unit defined for the MIL-100(Fe) system. This approach allows for a

consistent assessment of the environmental burdens associated solely with the production process, while acknowledging that the most functionally meaningful comparison would be based on the amount of material required to filter an equivalent volume of air, once such data become available.

The selected production processes from the Ecoinvent database and their corresponding quantities are summarised in Table 19.

Table 19: Overview of the SimaPro processes selected from the Ecoinvent v3.9.1 database for traditional filter materials (glass fibre and polypropylene granulate), each modelled with the same functional unit as MIL-100(Fe) (1 kton/year).

Material	SimaPro Process	Amount
MIL-100(Fe)	Production process of MIL-100(Fe)	1 kton/year
Glass Fibre	<i>Glass fibre {RER} cut-off, U</i>	1 kton/year
Polypropylene Granulate	<i>Polypropylene granulate {RER} polypropylene production, granulate cut-off, U</i>	1 kton/year

4.3 Impact Assessment

The Impact Assessment phase translates the data obtained in the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) into potential environmental impacts. In this study, the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) approach was adopted using the EF 3.1 (adapted) method implemented in SimaPro v9.6.0.1. This method was selected for its alignment with the European Commission's recommendations and its robustness in representing multiple midpoint environmental categories. The impact categories included in the EF 3.1 (adapted) method are briefly described below:

- **Climate change** indicates radiative forcing and the Global Warming Potential (GWP100), expressed in kg CO₂-equivalents (kg CO₂ eq). This category accounts for emissions of greenhouse gases such as CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O that contribute to global temperature increase.
- **Ozone depletion** uses the Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP) as an indicator, expressed in kg CFC-11 equivalents (kg CFC-11 eq), reflecting the reduction of the stratospheric ozone layer caused by halogenated compounds such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs).
- **Ionising radiation, human health** refers to human exposure to ionising radiation from radionuclide emissions and is expressed in kilobecquerels of uranium-235 equivalents (kBq U-235 eq).
- **Photochemical ozone formation, human health** represents the increase of tropospheric (ground-level) ozone concentrations that negatively affect human health, expressed in kg NMVOC equivalents (kg NMVOC eq), where NMVOC stands for non-methane volatile organic compounds.
- **Particulate matter** quantifies the impact of inhalable fine particles (PM_{2.5} and smaller) on human health, expressed as disease incidence, indicating the expected number of health cases associated with particulate emissions.

- **Acidification** measures the potential increase in environmental acidity in terrestrial and aquatic systems caused by emissions of acidifying substances (SO₂, NO_x, NH₃), expressed in moles of hydrogen ion equivalents (mol H⁺ eq).
- **Eutrophication, freshwater** quantifies the potential accumulation of nutrients, mainly phosphorus compounds, in freshwater ecosystems, expressed in kilograms of phosphorus equivalents (kg P eq).
- **Eutrophication, marine** represents nutrient enrichment in marine environments, primarily from nitrogen compounds, and is expressed in kilograms of nitrogen equivalents (kg N eq).
- **Eutrophication, terrestrial** quantifies nutrient deposition to soils caused mainly by nitrogen emissions, expressed in moles of nitrogen equivalents (mol N eq).
- **Human toxicity, cancer** quantifies the potential increase in lifetime cancer cases associated with exposure to carcinogenic substances, expressed in Comparative Toxic Units for humans (CTUh).
- **Human toxicity, non-cancer** measures the potential for non-carcinogenic health effects resulting from exposure to toxic substances, also expressed in CTUh.
- **Ecotoxicity, freshwater** assesses the potential for chemical emissions to harm freshwater ecosystems, expressed in Comparative Toxic Units for ecosystems (CTUe).
- **Land use** reflects the environmental impacts related to land occupation and transformation, considering effects on soil quality, erosion resistance, and biodiversity loss. It is expressed in points, corresponding to a dimensionless soil quality index.
- **Resource use, energy carriers (fossil fuels)** evaluates the depletion of non-renewable fossil energy resources and is expressed in megajoules (MJ).
- **Resource use, mineral and metals** measures the depletion of abiotic mineral and metal resources, expressed in kilograms of antimony equivalents (kg Sb eq).
- **Water use** quantifies the amount of freshwater consumed, weighted by regional water scarcity factors, expressed in cubic meters world equivalents (m³ world eq)

After normalisation and weighting, the results of the different impact categories can be aggregated to obtain a **single score**, which represents the overall environmental impact of the analysed system. This allows for a comprehensive interpretation of the results and facilitates the comparison between different systems or scenarios.

4.4 Interpretation

In this study, the Interpretation phase focuses on the analysis and discussion of the results obtained from the impact assessment, with the aim of identifying the main environmental hotspots and evaluating the overall sustainability of the scaled-up production process of MIL-100(Fe). The analysis examines the contribution of each process stage, i.e. reaction, filtration, drying, milling and storage, to the different impact categories, highlighting those with the highest environmental relevance.

Furthermore, this phase includes a comparative assessment between the environmental impact of MIL-100(Fe) and that of the materials used in traditional filtration systems commonly adopted in GLAM environments, namely glass fibres for HEPA filters and polypropylene granulate for MERV-13 filters. This comparison provides a contextual understanding of the relative sustainability of MIL-100(Fe) as a potential alternative for air purification applications.

The results and discussion of this phase are presented in Chapter 5, which details the identification of hotspots, the contribution of each process step to the overall impact and the interpretation of the findings. This stage also enables the formulation of conclusions, study's limitations and recommendations for improving the environmental performance of the MIL-100(Fe) production process and for guiding future developments of sustainable filtration materials.

5 Results and discussion

This chapter presents and discusses the results obtained from the Life Cycle Assessment of the scaled-up production of MIL-100(Fe). The aim is to identify the main environmental impacts and hotspots across the process stages and to compare the results with conventional filtration materials used in GLAM environments.

5.1 Diagnostic analysis of MIL-100(Fe) production process

The diagnostic analysis aims to identify the most significant sources of environmental burden within the scaled-up process of MIL-100(Fe). The characterization results obtained through the EF 3.1 method provide the environmental impact values for all sixteen midpoint categories, both for the overall process and for each individual production stage. These data are reported in Table 20.

Each impact categories is expressed in its specific reference unit, therefore direct numerical comparison between categories is not meaningful. However, the data allow the identification of the most impacting process stage within each category.

Overall, the reaction and drying stages clearly dominate the environmental profile across most categories. The reaction step shows the highest contributions in categories such as *Acidification*, *Climate change*, *Eutrophication*, *freshwater* and *Human toxicity*, primarily due to the intensive use of chemical reagents (iron salts, organic linkers and NaOH) and the energy demand. The drying stage also exerts substantial influence, particularly in categories linked to energy use, e.g., *Resource use*, *fossils* and *Climate change*, as it requires significant thermal energy input in the form of steam.

The filtration and milling steps exhibit moderate impacts, primarily linked to water use and electricity consumption, respectively, while the storage stage has negligible effects across all categories, as expected.

Since the different impact categories are measured in distinct units, the characterised results were normalised using the EF 3.1 normalisation factors, generating dimensionless scores that are reported in Table 21. Based on these normalised values, a Pareto analysis was performed to identify which impact categories contribute most significantly to the total environmental burden of the MIL-100(Fe) production process. The resulting Pareto plot, shown in Figure 6, illustrates the relative contribution of each category to the total normalised impact. The analysis indicates that approximately 80% of the total environmental impact is concentrated in five key categories: *Eutrophication*, *freshwater*, *Resource use*, *fossils*, *Human toxicity*, *cancer*, *Ecotoxicity*, *freshwater*, and *Climate change*.

Table 20: Characterisation data obtained applying the EF 3.1 method (adapted) in SimaPro to the entire production process of MIL-100(Fe).

Impact category	Unit	Total	Reaction	Filtration	Drying	Milling	Storage
Acidification	mol H+ eq	9.83E+04	7.55E+04	2.46E+01	2.27E+04	1.10E+02	0.00E+00
Climate change	kg CO2 eq	2.36E+07	1.51E+07	5.00E+03	8.48E+06	2.16E+04	0.00E+00
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	3.60E+08	3.33E+08	1.64E+06	2.47E+07	1.31E+05	0.00E+00
Particulate matter	disease inc.	5.31E-01	2.88E-01	2.21E-04	2.42E-01	3.83E-04	0.00E+00
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	1.76E+04	1.37E+04	1.17E+02	3.72E+03	1.90E+01	0.00E+00
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	1.36E+04	1.27E+04	1.41E+01	9.04E+02	1.92E+01	0.00E+00
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	1.54E+05	1.15E+05	5.98E+01	3.88E+04	1.65E+02	0.00E+00
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	5.75E-02	3.47E-02	4.16E-05	2.26E-02	4.31E-05	0.00E+00
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	1.46E-01	1.22E-01	4.55E-04	2.39E-02	1.65E-04	0.00E+00
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	9.41E+06	9.19E+06	1.60E+03	1.96E+05	1.42E+04	0.00E+00
Land use	Pt	6.79E+07	5.96E+07	2.45E+04	8.17E+06	8.65E+04	0.00E+00
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	6.02E-01	3.49E-01	1.14E-03	2.52E-01	3.73E-04	0.00E+00
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	6.11E+04	4.11E+04	1.53E+01	1.99E+04	5.48E+01	0.00E+00
Resource use, fossils	MJ	4.85E+08	3.63E+08	7.76E+04	1.21E+08	5.09E+05	0.00E+00
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	4.84E+01	4.56E+01	3.10E-02	2.74E+00	4.70E-02	0.00E+00
Water use	m3 depriv.	4.74E+06	4.45E+06	6.08E+04	2.21E+05	5.74E+03	0.00E+00

Table 21: Normalised values for each impact categories obtained applying the EF 3.1 method in SimaPro. These data are non-dimensional data, because they are normalised

Damage category	Total	Reaction	Filtration	Drying	Milling	Storage
Eutrophication, freshwater	8.46E+03	7.88E+03	8.76E+00	5.63E+02	1.19E+01	0.00E+00
Resource use, fossils	7.46E+03	5.59E+03	1.19E+00	1.86E+03	7.83E+00	0.00E+00
Human toxicity, cancer	3.33E+03	2.01E+03	2.41E+00	1.31E+03	2.50E+00	0.00E+00
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	3.17E+03	2.94E+03	1.45E+01	2.18E+02	1.15E+00	0.00E+00
Climate change	3.13E+03	2.00E+03	6.61E-01	1.12E+03	2.86E+00	0.00E+00
Ionising radiation	2.23E+03	2.18E+03	3.78E-01	4.65E+01	3.37E+00	0.00E+00
Acidification	1.77E+03	1.36E+03	4.42E-01	4.09E+02	1.97E+00	0.00E+00
Photochemical ozone formation	1.50E+03	1.01E+03	3.74E-01	4.87E+02	1.34E+00	0.00E+00
Human toxicity, non-cancer	1.14E+03	9.46E+02	3.53E+00	1.86E+02	1.28E+00	0.00E+00
Eutrophication, marine	9.00E+02	7.02E+02	5.97E+00	1.91E+02	9.73E-01	0.00E+00
Particulate matter	8.92E+02	4.84E+02	3.71E-01	4.07E+02	6.43E-01	0.00E+00
Eutrophication, terrestrial	8.71E+02	6.50E+02	3.39E-01	2.20E+02	9.35E-01	0.00E+00
Resource use, minerals and metals	7.61E+02	7.17E+02	4.87E-01	4.30E+01	7.39E-01	0.00E+00
Water use	4.13E+02	3.88E+02	5.30E+00	1.93E+01	5.01E-01	0.00E+00
Land use	8.28E+01	7.27E+01	2.99E-02	9.97E+00	1.06E-01	0.00E+00
Ozone depletion	1.15E+01	6.67E+00	2.17E-02	4.80E+00	7.13E-03	0.00E+00

Figure 6: Pareto analysis showing the contribution of each impact category to the total normalised environmental impact of MIL-100(Fe) production, calculated using the EF 3.1 method.

Among these, *Eutrophication, freshwater* shows the highest contribution, primarily driven by nutrient emissions (phosphorus and nitrogen compounds) resulting from reagent consumption and wastewater discharges during the reaction stage. *Resource use, fossils* also emerge as a critical category, reflecting the high energy demand of drying and milling operations, which rely on fossil-based energy sources. *Human toxicity, cancer* and *Ecotoxicity, freshwater* are influenced by the chemical inputs used during synthesis, whereas *Climate change* correlates mainly with energy consumption and process emissions.

To further analyse the distribution of impacts among process stages, Figure 7 presents the normalized contributions of each stage across the five most critical impact categories.

Figure 7: Normalised contribution of each production stage (reaction, filtration, drying, milling, and storage) to the most critical impact categories identified for the MIL-100(Fe) production process.

The results indicate that the reaction stage is the dominant contributor in all categories, representing the primary environmental hotspot of the process. This stage accounts for over 90% of the total impact in *Eutrophication, freshwater* and *Ecotoxicity, freshwater*, confirming its central role in determining the overall footprint of MIL-100(Fe) production. This predominance is attributed to several concurrent factors: the large amounts of chemical precursors required ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, BTC, and NaOH), the associated emissions to water containing sulphates, nitrates and residual organic compounds, and the energy input necessary to sustain the reaction conditions. Moreover, the subsequent wastewater treatment and effluent discharges increase nutrient loading, thereby intensifying the eutrophication potential. The combination of reagent-related impacts and process energy demand thus makes the reaction phase the most environmentally burdensome step within the system.

The drying stage follows as the second major contributor, particularly in *Resource use, fossils*, *Human toxicity, cancer* and *Climate change*, due to its high thermal energy requirements for solvent evaporation and material stabilization. In contrast, the filtration and milling stages show comparatively lower contributions, though they remain relevant for categories associated with mechanical energy use. The storage stage, on the other hand, has negligible environmental relevance, confirming that most impacts are generated upstream, during reaction and drying.

To provide a clearer visualization of the relative contributions of each subprocess to the overall environmental performance, Sankey diagrams (Figure 8-12) were generated in SimaPro for the entire MIL-100(Fe) production process (“Production process”). These diagrams display the normalized results for the five impact categories considered, applying a 2% cut-off threshold to exclude minor contributions

and highlight the most influential flows. Consistent with the Pareto analysis, the reaction and drying stages emerge as the dominant contributors across nearly all categories, confirming their central role as environmental hotspots within the production system.

The Sankey diagram shown in Figure 8 illustrates the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category *Eutrophication, freshwater* (2% cut-off). The diagram clearly highlights the reaction stage as the dominant contributor, mainly due to the combined influence of BTC consumption and electricity use, which together account for more than 90% of the total impact in this category.

Figure 8: Sankey diagram for the MIL-100(Fe) production process (cut-off: 2%), showing the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category *Eutrophication, freshwater*.

Similarly, Figure 9 illustrates the Sankey diagram for the impact category *Resource use, fossils*. In this case, the reaction and drying stages remain the main contributors to the overall impact, accounting together for the vast majority of fossil resource consumption. The reaction step dominates primarily due to the electricity demand required for mechanical stirring and process control, as well as the production and supply of chemical reagents such as BTC, trimethylbenzene and chloromethane, which are derived from fossil-based feedstocks. The drying stage further contributes through the steam generation process, which relies on heat produced from fossil fuels. These combined effects confirm the strong dependence of the system on non-renewable energy sources, highlighting the importance of integrating renewable electricity and waste heat recovery strategies to enhance process sustainability.

Figure 9: Sankey diagram for the entire MIL-100(Fe) production process (cut-off: 2%), showing the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category *Resource use, fossils*.

In Figure 10, the Sankey diagram illustrates the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category *Human toxicity, cancer*. Also in this case, it is possible to observe that both the reaction and the drying stages significantly influence this impact category, accounting approximately 60% and 40% of the total contribution, respectively.

The reaction stage exerts the largest effect, primarily due to the use of BTC, trimethylbenzene and chloromethane, as well as their precursors (e.g., benzene, methanol and hydrochloric acid), which are associated with toxic emissions during their upstream production. While the drying process further

contributes through steam generation and energy use, which introduce additional emissions linked to fuel combustion.

Figure 10: Sankey diagram for the entire MIL-100(Fe) production process (cut-off: 2%), showing the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category *Human toxicity, cancer*.

Figure 11 shows the contribution of the input and output flows to the impact category *Ecotoxicity, freshwater*. The reaction stage accounts for more than 90% of the total impact, primarily due to nutrient contained in the wastewater flows, as well as the production and use of chemical reagents, such as BTC

and trimethylbenzene. The drying step provides a minor contribution, mainly related to the steam generation.

Figure 11: Sankey diagram for the entire MIL-100(Fe) production process (cut-off: 2%), showing the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category Ecotoxicity, freshwater.

In Figure 12, the Sankey diagram for the Climate change category highlights the reaction and drying stages as the predominant contributors, representing about 64% and 36% of the total impact, respectively.

The reaction stage is mainly affected by the electricity consumption required for process operation and by upstream emissions from reagent production. The drying stage further contributes through steam generation powered by fossil-based fuels, reinforcing the link between thermal energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

Figure 12: Sankey diagram for the entire MIL-100(Fe) production process (cut-off: 2%), showing the contribution of the main input and output flows to the impact category *Climate change*.

Overall, the diagnostic analysis highlights two main environmental hotspots: energy-intensive operations, particularly thermal energy use in drying and chemical reagent consumption and wastewater management in the reaction stage. These findings suggest that targeted improvements in process energy efficiency and reagent recovery could significantly reduce the overall environmental footprint of MIL-100(Fe) production.

Overall, the diagnostic analysis identifies two major environmental hotspots within the MIL-100(Fe) production process: the reaction stage, driven by chemical reagent consumption, wastewater generation, and high electricity demand, and the drying stage, characterised by intensive thermal energy use. These findings indicate that the environmental performance of the process is primarily influenced by energy consumption (both electrical and thermal) and by the use and disposal of chemical inputs. As a result, targeted process improvements focusing on energy efficiency, integration of renewable electricity, reagent and solvent recovery, and wastewater management could substantially reduce the overall environmental footprint and enhance the sustainability of MIL-100(Fe) production.

5.1.1 Hotspot identification in the leading environmental impact stage

Following the identification of the reaction as the most environmentally impactful stage, a detailed analysis was conducted to determine the specific input and output flows that contribute most significantly to the overall environmental burden. The evaluation focuses on the five most critical impact categories identified in the Section 5.1: *Eutrophication, freshwater*, *Resource use, fossils*, *Human toxicity, cancer*, *Ecotoxicity, freshwater* and *Climate change*.

For each category, Sankey diagrams (Figures 13–17) were generated in SimaPro to visualise the contribution of the main flows to the total impact of the reaction stage. The normalised values of all input and output flows for this step are reported in Table C.1 (Appendix C), allowing for a clearer comparison of the relative contributions, as all results are expressed in the same unit of measure.

Figure 13 shows that electricity (*Electricity, medium voltage {RER} | market group for | Cut-off, U*) is the dominant hotspot within the *Eutrophication, freshwater* impact category, accounting for over 94% of the total contribution. This result reflects the high energy demand of thermal and mechanical operations required during the reaction phase. The impact is further amplified by the fossil-based composition of the regional electricity mix. In comparison, the contribution of BTC remains marginal, representing only about 3% of the total impact.

Figure 13: Sankey diagram of the impact category *Eutrophication, freshwater*, based on normalised values (cut-off: 2%) for the reaction step of MIL-100(Fe) production process.

Figure 14 shows that electricity consumption represents the dominant contributor ($\approx 88\%$) to the *Resource use, fossils* impact category, confirming its strong influence due to the fossil-based energy mix of the European region. The high electricity demand during reaction control and agitation directly drives fossil fuel depletion.

Secondary yet relevant contributions are observed for BTC ($\approx 11\%$) and trimethylbenzene ($\approx 10\%$), whose upstream production involves energy-intensive synthesis routes and the use of organic solvents derived from petrochemical feedstocks. Smaller contributions from methanol and chloromethane are also detected, which are linked to the use of fossil-derived reagents in precursor preparation.

Overall, this pattern underscores the significant role of energy supply and organic chemical inputs in determining the fossil resource depletion associated with the reaction stage of MIL-100(Fe) production.

Figure 14: Sankey diagram of the impact category *Resource use, fossils*, based on normalised values (cut-off: 2%) for the reaction step of MIL-100(Fe) production process.

Observing the Sankey diagram for the *Human toxicity, cancer* impact category (Figure 15), electricity consumption once again represents the largest contribution ($\approx 78\%$), confirming its dominant role across most environmental categories. This impact is mainly associated with the fossil-based electricity mix and the high energy demand required during the reaction step. Secondary but still relevant contributions are observed for BTC ($\approx 16\%$) and trimethylbenzene ($\approx 15\%$), both linked to the use of organic solvents and the potential release of toxic intermediates during their synthesis. Additionally, iron sulphate ($\approx 3\%$)

and hydrochloric acid ($\approx 5\%$) contribute moderately, primarily due to upstream emissions of heavy metals and by-products from chemical manufacturing processes. Overall, these results highlight that energy supply and reagent production are the key drivers of human toxicity impacts in the reaction stage.

Figure 15: Sankey diagram of the impact category *Human toxicity, cancer*, based on normalised values (cut-off: 2%) for the reaction step of MIL-100(Fe) production process.

Figure 16 shows that BTC is the dominant contributor ($\approx 71\%$) to the Ecotoxicity, freshwater impact category, closely followed by trimethylbenzene ($\approx 70\%$). These contributions are mainly associated with the potential release of aromatic compounds and organic intermediates that exhibit strong ecotoxic effects on aquatic ecosystems during synthesis and processing. Electricity consumption accounts for a smaller yet notable share ($\approx 25\%$), reflecting the indirect impacts of fossil-based power generation.

Finally, wastewater flows ($\approx 2\%$) also contribute to this category, highlighting the role of discharge streams in shaping the ecotoxicity profile of the reaction stage.

Figure 17 presents the Sankey diagram for the *Climate change* impact category, showing that electricity consumption is once again the dominant contributor ($\approx 90\%$). This reflects its direct link to CO_2 emissions

Figure 16: Sankey diagram of the impact category *Ecotoxicity, freshwater*, based on normalised values (cut-off: 2%) for the reaction step of MIL-100(Fe) production process.

resulting from fossil-based electricity generation. BTC ($\approx 9\%$) and trimethylbenzene ($\approx 7\%$) follow as secondary contributors.

The results shown in Figure 17 confirm that the global warming potential (GWP) of the reaction stage is primarily driven by indirect emissions from energy generation and the high energy demand associated with chemical reagent synthesis.

Overall, the analysed Sankey diagrams (Figure 13-17) confirm that the dominant hotspots in the reaction stage are associated with electricity consumption, mainly due to the fossil-based energy mix, and with the synthesis of BTC, whose upstream production involves energy-intensive organic reactions and the use of petrochemical precursors.

These findings highlight that the environmental performance of the process is largely driven by energy demand and chemical reagent production. Consequently, improving energy efficiency, integrating renewable electricity and optimising precursor synthesis routes represent the most effective strategies to mitigate the overall environmental footprint of MIL-100(Fe) production and to enhance its sustainability at industrial scale.

5.1.2 Hotspots identification in the second-highest impact stage

As observed in Figure 7, the drying stage represents the second-largest contributor to the overall environmental impact of the MIL-100(Fe) production process, following the reaction stage. The Sankey diagram presented in Figure 18 illustrates the distribution of environmental burdens within this step, focusing on the *Eutrophication, freshwater* impact category. The normalised values of the input and output flows related to the drying step are reported in Table C.2 (Appendix C), providing a clearer overview of the relative contributions of each flow to the total impact.

The results clearly indicate that heat generation from steam (*Heat, from steam, in chemical industry* {RER} | *market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry* | *Cut-off, U*) constitutes the dominant hotspot in this process stage. The use of steam is essential for solvent evaporation, removal of residual moisture and stabilization of the crystalline structure of the MIL-100(Fe) powder [6]. However, the production of this thermal energy is typically associated with fossil-based fuel combustion, which leads to indirect nutrient emissions contributing to eutrophication.

This finding is consistent with the trends observed in other most critical impact categories, i.e. *Resource use, fossils, Human toxicity, cancer, Ecotoxicity, freshwater* and *Climate change*, where thermal energy demand plays a major role. The strong dependence of the drying stage on externally supplied steam makes it one of the most energy-intensive operations in the entire process, amplifying its environmental significance.

Figure 18: Sankey diagram of the impact category *Eutrophication, freshwater*, based on normalised values (cut-off: 2%) for the drying step of MIL-100(Fe) production process.

To mitigate these impacts, improvements should target thermal efficiency and energy source optimization. Potential strategies include the implementation of waste heat recovery systems, the integration of renewable energy sources for steam generation and the optimization of drying parameters (e.g., temperature, airflow and residence time) to minimize energy use without compromising product quality. Applying these measures could significantly reduce the environmental footprint of the drying stage and contribute to a more sustainable industrial-scale production of MIL-100(Fe).

5.2 Comparison with the traditional filters (HEPA and MERV-13) used in GLAMs

This section compares the production process of MIL-100(Fe), the MOF investigated in this study, with the materials used for conventional air filtration systems commonly employed in HVAC systems of GLAM institutions. Specifically, the comparison involves the production process of *Glass fibre {RER} | cut-off, U* for HEPA filters and *Polypropylene granulate {RER} | polypropylene production, granulate | cut-off, U* for MERV-13 filters, both sourced from the Ecoinvent database [3].

To ensure methodological consistency, the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 (adapted) method was applied in SimaPro to all production systems, maintaining the same functional unit (1 kton/year) adopted for MIL-100(Fe).

The characterisation results obtained for the three materials are reported in Table 22, which shows the impact values for each EF 3.1 midpoint category, expressed in the corresponding reference units. In the table, higher contributions are highlighted in red, indicating the most environmentally burdensome processes for each category, while lower values are marked in green, representing the least impactful options.

Table 22: Comparison of the characterisation data obtained for the production processes of MIL-100(Fe), HEPA filter material (Glass fibre) and MERV-13 filter material (Polypropylene granulate), considering the same FU (1 kton/year).

Impact category	Unit	MIL-100(Fe)	HEPA*	MERV-13**
Acidification	mol H+ eq	9.83E+04	1.60E+04	7.16E+03
Climate change	kg CO2 eq	2.36E+07	2.14E+06	2.37E+06
Ecotoxicity, freshwater		3.60E+08	1.54E+07	1.66E+07
Particulate matter	disease inc.	5.31E-01	1.02E-01	5.66E-02
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	1.76E+04	3.26E+03	1.42E+03
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	1.36E+04	6.51E+02	4.25E+02
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	1.54E+05	3.44E+04	1.47E+04
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	5.75E-02	6.16E-03	9.03E-03
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	1.46E-01	1.27E-01	1.97E-02
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	9.41E+06	3.70E+05	1.70E+05
Land use	Pt	6.79E+07	5.79E+06	6.69E+06
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	6.02E-01	5.09E-02	1.08E-01
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	6.11E+04	1.08E+04	1.28E+04
Resource use, fossils	MJ	4.85E+08	3.37E+07	7.55E+07
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	4.84E+01	2.92E+02	2.11E+01
Water use	m3 depriv.	4.74E+06	6.56E+05	1.10E+06

(*) HEPA filter material: Glass fibre

(**) MERV-13 filter material: Polypropylene granulate

Overall, the comparison reveals that MIL-100(Fe) exhibits higher impacts in several categories, e.g. *Eutrophication, freshwater, Resource use, fossils* and *Human toxicity, cancer*, mainly due to its energy- and reagent-intensive synthesis. Conversely, polypropylene granulate shows the lowest overall impacts, reflecting the maturity and efficiency of polymer production technologies, while glass fibre occupies an intermediate position, with relevant contributions in *Particulate matter* and *Land use* due to raw material extraction and high-temperature processing.

These results indicate that, while MIL-100(Fe) production currently entails a greater environmental burden, its potential as an advanced filtration material lies in future process optimisation and integration with renewable energy sources, which could significantly reduce its footprint and improve its competitiveness compared to conventional materials.

5.2.1 Comparison between the production of MIL-100(Fe) and HEPA material

The comparison between the production process of MIL-100(Fe) and the one of *Glass fibre {RER} | cut-off, U*, which is the material that HEPA filters are made of, revealed that MIL-100(Fe) exhibits significantly higher environmental impacts across almost all categories (Figure 19). This trend is consistent with the characterisation data reported in Table 22. The normalised values used to obtain these plots are reported in Table C.3 (Appendix C).

Figure 19: Comparison between the contribution of the production processes of MIL-100(Fe) and of HEPA filter material (Glass fibre), expressed as normalised values, on all the impact categories of the EF 3.1 (adapted) method.

In Figure 19, the contrast between the two materials is particularly evident: MIL-100(Fe) dominates nearly every impact category, confirming the greater environmental intensity of its synthesis process. The results indicate that the reaction and drying stages, previously identified as the most energy- and resource-demanding steps, are primarily responsible for this outcome. In particular, the *Eutrophication, freshwater* and *Human toxicity* categories are strongly influenced by the consumption of chemical reagents (e.g., $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaOH, and BTC) and by wastewater generation, while *Resource use, fossils* and *Climate change* are driven by high electricity and steam demand. These effects are further amplified by the reliance on a fossil-based energy mix in the reference region (RER).

The only exception is observed in Figure 19 for *Resource use, minerals and metals* category, where the glass fibre process shows a higher contribution. This is mainly due to the extraction and processing of mineral raw materials, such as silica and alumina, required for fibre manufacturing, which involve intensive mining and high-temperature melting processes [11], [22].

It is also important to note that this comparison was performed considering the same functional unit (1 kton/year) for all materials. This methodological choice ensures consistency in the assessment of production-related burdens but does not account for the differences in filtration performance between

materials. Literature reports that MIL-100(Fe) exhibits superior adsorption and filtration capacities compared to conventional HEPA filters, particularly for volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and fine particulate matter [4], [6], [49]. Consequently, an equivalent air purification performance would likely require a smaller amount of MIL-100(Fe) than glass fibre. A more functionally meaningful comparison should therefore be based on the amount of material required to filter an equivalent volume of air, once sufficient experimental data become available.

Moreover, it should be considered that MIL-100(Fe) synthesis represents a relatively recent and still developing technology, whereas the production of glass fibre is a well-established and highly optimised industrial process. The higher impacts observed for MIL-100(Fe) thus reflect not only the intrinsic complexity of its synthesis but also the lower technological maturity and optimisation level of its current large-scale production routes.

Overall, the comparison demonstrates that while MIL-100(Fe) currently presents a higher environmental burden than traditional HEPA materials, this outcome is closely linked to its synthesis pathway and energy configuration, rather than to the intrinsic properties of the material. The LCA results and supporting literature suggest several possible strategies to reduce these impacts:

- Replacing conventional heating with microwave- or ultrasound-assisted synthesis, as proposed by *Laybourn et al. (2017)*, which enables shorter reaction times, more precise control over crystal size and higher energy efficiency compared to traditional heating [52];
- Recovering heat from the drying stage through Waste Heat Recovery (WHR) systems, which offer promising solutions to improve overall thermal process efficiency and reduce fossil fuel consumption, thereby enhancing both heating and energy generation performance [53];
- Transitioning to renewable electricity sources within the process energy mix to further reduce the carbon footprint of MIL-100(Fe) production.

The implementation of these measures could significantly mitigate the impacts in the *Resource use*, *fossils* and *Climate change* categories, narrowing the environmental gap between MIL-100(Fe) and conventional filtration materials such as glass fibre.

5.2.2 Comparison between the production of MIL-100(Fe) and MERV-13 material

The MERV-13 filter, widely used in GLAM HVAC systems within GLAM institutions, typically employs polypropylene fibres as the main filtration medium, due to their mechanical resistance and relatively low production cost [3], [11]. However, polypropylene is a fossil-based polymer and its manufacturing process involves petrochemical refining and polymerization, which are both energy- and emission-intensive operations.

Applying the EF 3.1 (adapted) method to both the production processes enables a comparison to be made between the synthesis of MIL-100(Fe) and the production of *Polypropylene granulate* {*RER*} | *cut-off, U*. The normalised values obtained are reported in Table C.4 (Appendix C).

As illustrated in Figure 20, MIL-100(Fe) exhibits substantially higher environmental impacts across all the categories. The trend closely mirrors that observed for the comparison with the HEPA filter material (Section 5.2.1). The reaction and drying stages of MIL-100(Fe) production again emerge as the primary contributors to the total impact, largely due to electricity and thermal energy consumption, as well as the use of chemical reagents with high upstream burdens.

Conversely, polypropylene production shows relatively higher values in *Resource use, minerals and metals*, mainly attributable to the catalysts, stabilisers and additives required for polymerization, as well as to the extraction of metallic elements used in catalyst preparation.

Figure 20: Comparison between the contribution of the production processes of MIL-100(Fe) and of MERV-13 filter material (Polypropylene granulate), expressed as normalised values, on all the impact categories of the EF 3.1 (adapted) method.

As also highlighted in the previous section, this comparison is based on the same functional unit (1 kton/year) for both systems. While this ensures methodological consistency, it does not account for potential differences in filtration performance between the materials. Literature reports that MOFs possess superior adsorption and filtration properties compared to conventional polymer-based filters, particularly for volatile organic compounds and fine particulate matter [6], [49]. Therefore, a functionally equivalent comparison, based on the amount of material required to filter an equivalent air volume, could

yield different results. In theory, a smaller quantity of MIL-100(Fe) would be needed to achieve the same air purification efficiency as MERV-13, potentially lowering its relative environmental impact once this parameter is experimentally quantified. Future research should therefore aim to integrate experimental filtration capacity data into the LCA framework to enable a more performance-based comparison.

Overall, the comparison confirms that MIL-100(Fe) currently shows a higher environmental footprint than polypropylene, largely due to its energy-intensive and less industrially optimised synthesis route. To enhance its environmental performance, the strategies discussed in Section 5.2.1, including the integration of renewable energy sources, the adoption of waste heat recovery systems and the optimisation of BTC synthesis, remain highly relevant. Implementing these measures could help position MIL-100(Fe) as a viable low-impact alternative to traditional filtration materials, particularly when considering its superior adsorption performance as demonstrated in previous studies [5], [6].

5.2.3 Sensitivity analysis: the influence of MIL-100(Fe) production quantity

To further explore how the quantity of MIL-100(Fe) produced influences its overall environmental performance, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by varying the production amount in the Life Cycle model. In Life Cycle Assessment, the Single Score (SS) represents an aggregated indicator that combines all midpoint impact categories into a single numerical value, expressed in kPt (kilo points). This value provides a synthetic measure of the total environmental burden of a system, facilitating comparison among different scenarios or materials.

In this analysis, the production quantity of MIL-100(Fe) was progressively reduced in SimaPro by varying the number of produced units (“pieces”) from 1 p (corresponding to 1 kton/year) to 0.8 p, 0.6 p, 0.5 p, 0.4 p. The corresponding Single Scores for each scenario were calculated using the EF 3.1 (adapted) method and compared with those of the traditional filter materials: HEPA (glass fibre) and MERV-13 (polypropylene granulate). The results are summarised in Figure 21.

As shown in Figure 21, the total Single Score decreases in an almost exponential trend with the reduction of MIL-100(Fe) production. The impact reduction is particularly pronounced between 1 p and 0.4 p, after which the curve flattens, indicating diminishing marginal reductions. This behaviour reflects the non-linear relationship between process scaling and environmental load.

Figure 21: Sensitivity analysis of the Single Score for MIL-100(Fe) at different production quantities, compared with HEPA and MERV-13 filter materials

The baseline scenario (MIL-100(Fe), 1 p) exhibits the highest overall burden, approximately 2.2 kPt, primarily due to the energy-intensive reaction and drying stages identified in the previous analyses. As production decreases to 0.5 p, the total impact is halved, around 1.1 kPt, and at 0.4 p it drops to close to 0.88 kPt, approaching the impact range of conventional filter materials.

For smaller production quantities of MIL-100(Fe), for example 0.3 p and 0.2 p, the Single Score becomes almost negligible, as the modelled system represents only a minimal fraction of the original process with proportionally reduced material and energy inputs. These results should therefore be regarded as theoretical lower limits rather than realistic scaled-up production scenarios.

Overall, the sensitivity analysis confirms that reducing the production quantity of MIL-100(Fe) substantially decreases its environmental footprint, with a trend approaching exponential decay. This

reduction brings the aggregated environmental performance of MIL-100(Fe) closer to that of HEPA and MERV-13 materials. Furthermore, considering the superior adsorption and filtration capacity of MIL-100(Fe) reported in literature, the actual amount required to achieve equivalent filtration efficiency is expected to be lower than that of traditional materials. Once these performance data become experimentally available, future LCA studies should perform **functionally equivalent comparisons**, based on the material quantity needed to filter a defined air volume rather than on mass-based equivalence.

Overall, the sensitivity analysis indicates that decreasing the production quantity of MIL-100(Fe) brings its total environmental impact closer to that of traditional filter materials, although it still remains higher. This difference can be attributed to the current modelling assumptions and the relatively early stage of the optimization of MIL-100(Fe) production process. With further process refinement and improved modelling accuracy, these impacts could be significantly reduced. Moreover, given the superior adsorption and filtration capacity of MIL-100(Fe) reported in the literature, the actual amount required to achieve equivalent filtration performance is expected to be lower than that of conventional materials. Once these performance data become experimentally available, future LCA studies should conduct functionally equivalent comparisons, based on the material quantity required to filter a defined air volume rather than on mass-based equivalence, allowing for a more accurate evaluation of the environmental benefits of MIL-100(Fe).

5.2.4 Discussion and conclusions on the comparison

The Life Cycle Assessment carried out in this thesis provided a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental performance of the scaled-up production of MIL-100(Fe) compared with conventional air filtration materials used in GLAM environments, namely glass fibre (HEPA filters) and polypropylene granulate (MERV-13 filters). The comparison aimed to contextualize the environmental profile of MIL-100(Fe) within existing filtration technologies and to assess whether its production could represent a sustainable alternative to current materials.

The results show that, when compared to traditional filter materials (Section 5.2), MIL-100(Fe) exhibits higher environmental impacts across almost all midpoint categories of the EF 3.1 (adapted) method. This outcome can be primarily attributed to the early technological development and limited optimization of its large-scale synthesis, which remains significantly more energy- and resource-intensive than the mature and industrially optimized production routes of glass fibre and polypropylene. In contrast, conventional filters benefit from decades of process refinement, higher energy efficiency, and stable yields, resulting in lower overall environmental burdens.

Nevertheless, the sensitivity analysis (Section 5.2.3) demonstrated that decreasing the production quantity of MIL-100(Fe) results in a non-linear (almost exponential) reduction in its total environmental burden. For lower production levels (0.4 p), the total impact approaches that of conventional filters. This indicates that, under real operating conditions where smaller quantities of MIL-100(Fe) would likely be

required to achieve equivalent filtration performance, its environmental performance could become comparable or even favourable.

Moreover, literature reports that MIL-100(Fe) exhibits superior adsorption and filtration capacity compared to polymeric or fibreglass-based filters [4], [6]. Consequently, a smaller amount of MIL-100(Fe) might suffice to purify the same air volume, potentially offsetting its higher production impacts. Once experimental filtration data become available, future LCAs should perform functionally equivalent comparisons, based on the mass required to treat an equivalent volume of air, rather than on the production of equal masses.

In light of these findings, several improvement strategies can be proposed:

- Integration of renewable electricity within the process energy mix to reduce dependence on fossil sources;
- Implementation of solvent-free or microwave-assisted synthesis routes, which have shown to minimize reaction time, solvent use, and energy consumption;
- Application of waste heat recovery systems in the drying stage to reduce thermal energy demand;
- Optimization of BTC synthesis to minimize reagent-related impacts, given its significant contribution to *Eutrophication* and *Ecotoxicity* categories.

In summary, while the current environmental footprint of MIL-100(Fe) production remains higher than that of traditional filtration materials, its superior functional efficiency, potential regenerability and durability highlight its promise as a next-generation material for sustainable air purification in GLAM environments. Future assessments that incorporate operational performance will be essential to confirm whether these advantages compensate for the production-stage burdens.

5.3 Limitations of the study and recommendations

Despite the robustness of the applied methodology and the consistency with ISO 14040 and 14044 standards, several limitations of this study must be acknowledged. These limitations arise from both modelling assumptions and data availability, and they influence the interpretation and transferability of the results.

5.3.1 Limitations of the modelling approach

The present LCA adopts a gate-to-gate system boundary, focusing exclusively on the core manufacturing stages of MIL-100(Fe), from raw material input to product storage. Upstream phases such as raw material extraction, reagent synthesis (e.g., BTC, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaOH), and energy production, as well as downstream processes such as use, maintenance and end-of-life, were excluded. This choice allows a focused evaluation of the synthesis process but inevitably limits the completeness of the environmental profile.

A cradle-to-gate or cradle-to-grave analysis would provide a more comprehensive understanding, especially once reliable industrial data for upstream production of reagents become available. Moreover, the current process model represents a scaled-up scenario rather than an actual industrial plant. As such, the results should be interpreted as indicative of potential trends rather than exact industrial-scale figures.

The model also relies partly on secondary data from literature and Ecoinvent v3.9.1, which may not perfectly represent the real physicochemical conditions or efficiency of large-scale synthesis. Similarly, certain process flows (e.g., wastewater composition) were simplified or aggregated to ensure consistency within SimaPro, potentially masking specific emissions or recovery opportunities.

5.3.2 Limitations of the functional comparison

Another critical limitation concerns the functional equivalence of the comparison with conventional filters. Since the filtration capacity and adsorption kinetics of MIL-100(Fe) have not yet been experimentally quantified at scale, the comparison with HEPA and MERV-13 filters materials was necessarily performed on a mass basis (1 kton/year). However, MIL-100(Fe) is expected to achieve equivalent or superior pollutant removal efficiency with a smaller amount of material, due to its higher specific surface area and affinity for VOCs. Therefore, the current comparison likely overestimates the relative environmental burden of MIL-100(Fe).

Furthermore, the study assesses only the production of the material, not the entire filter manufacturing process. In practice, a MIL-100(Fe)-based filter would include additional components such as binders, supports, or casings, whose impacts were not modelled here. It is also important to note that commercial HEPA and MERV-13 filters are typically single-use components that require periodic replacement, whereas MIL-based systems could be regenerated or reused multiple times. This characteristic would potentially translate into a longer operational lifespan and lower cumulative environmental impacts during the use phase.

5.3.3 Recommendations for future work

Future research should address the limitation described in the previous sections (Section 5.3.1 and 5.3.2) by:

- Extending the system boundaries to a cradle-to-gate or cradle-to-grave scope, including the production of reagents, transport, and filter integration stages;
- Performing functionally equivalent LCAs, based on the amount of MIL-100(Fe) required to filter a defined air volume or achieve a specified pollutant removal efficiency;
- Experimentally determining the filtration and adsorption performance of MIL-100(Fe) under real operating conditions to validate the LCA assumptions;

- Investigating energy recovery and circular strategies, such as solvent recycling, by-product valorisation, and renewable energy integration;
- Developing a Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social LCA (S-LCA) framework in parallel, to capture economic feasibility and social implications;
- Assessing filter lifespan, maintenance frequency and regeneration cycles in comparison to conventional filters, to quantify potential advantages over the full operational life.

By addressing these aspects, future LCAs will enable a more accurate and functionally relevant evaluation of MIL-100(Fe)'s environmental benefits, supporting its development as a truly sustainable alternative for air purification in GLAMs.

6 Conclusion

The primary objective of this thesis was to evaluate the environmental sustainability of the scaled-up production of the metal–organic framework MIL-100(Fe) through a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). The study aimed to quantify the environmental impacts associated with its synthesis, to identify the main hotspots along the production chain and to provide insights into the potential of this material as a sustainable alternative to traditional air filtration systems used in Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAMs). This research was carried out in the framework of the European SIMIACCI project, which promotes innovative and environmentally responsible solutions for indoor air quality management in the cultural and creative sectors.

The LCA performed in this work followed the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards and adopted a gate-to-gate approach, focusing on the main unit operations directly related to the production of MIL-100(Fe): reaction, filtration, drying, milling, and storage. The results obtained modelling the production process in SimaPro, demonstrated that the environmental performance of MIL-100(Fe) is primarily driven by the energy- and resource- consumption of certain process stages, particularly the reaction and drying steps.

The results of the LCA revealed that the reaction and drying stages are the main contributors to the overall environmental impact of MIL-100(Fe) synthesis. The reaction phase emerged as the most impactful phase in terms of *Eutrophication, freshwater, Resource use, fossils, Human toxicity, cancer, Ecotoxicity, freshwater* and *Climate change*, largely due to the high consumption of electricity and chemical precursors, as BTC. The drying step, on the other hand, was identified as the second hotspot step due to the intensive use of heat from steam as a thermal energy source. These findings indicate that improvements in energy efficiency and heat recovery could significantly reduce the environmental burden of large-scale MIL-100(Fe) production. Other process stages, such as filtration, milling, and storage, showed comparatively lower impacts but remain relevant when considering cumulative contributions and potential efficiency gains. For instance, the optimization of milling operations and the adoption of more efficient mechanical systems could reduce electricity consumption, while the implementation of closed-loop water systems in filtration could minimize wastewater generation.

From a broader perspective, the comparison between MIL-100(Fe) and conventional filtration technologies such as HEPA and MERV-13 filters highlights both the challenges and opportunities of MOF-based systems. On one hand, MIL-100(Fe) exhibits higher production impacts, mainly due to its early-stage process maturity and the energy-intensive nature of its synthesis. However, the sensitivity analysis demonstrated that reducing the production quantity, or equivalently, employing smaller amounts of material, significantly decreases the overall Single Score, bringing MIL-100(Fe)'s environmental footprint closer to that of traditional filters.

On the other hand, MOF-based filtration materials such as MIL-100(Fe) present promising long-term advantages over conventional filters, which are typically single-use and rely on polymeric materials with limited recyclability. Their potential for regeneration and reuse could reduce material waste and operational costs, while their high adsorption capacity and structural tunability enable selective pollutant removal under mild conditions. These features could ultimately enhance both the energy efficiency of HVAC systems and the preservation of cultural heritage environments. Nonetheless, realising these benefits will depend on effectively mitigating the environmental burden of MIL-100(Fe) synthesis through cleaner energy integration and process optimisation.

The results of this study represent the first quantitative benchmark for assessing the environmental sustainability of MIL-100(Fe) production at a scaled-up level. They also demonstrate that while the material exhibits remarkable potential as an innovative sorbent, its environmental performance strongly depends on process parameters, energy sources and material recovery strategies. Future research should therefore aim at integrating solvent-free synthesis, microwave-assisted reactions and renewable energy inputs to minimize the life cycle footprint of production. Similarly, the valorisation of by-products or effluents could transform waste streams into secondary resources, further aligning the process with circular economy principles.

This study also highlights several methodological opportunities. The gate-to-gate system boundaries adopted here provided a focused understanding of the manufacturing process but excluded upstream and downstream phases, such as raw material extraction, transportation, use, and end-of-life management. Expanding the system to a cradle-to-grave perspective in future work would enable a more comprehensive sustainability assessment and support more accurate decision-making.

Furthermore, integrating Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) would allow the evaluation of economic and social dimensions alongside environmental performance, advancing towards a full Triple Bottom Line (TBL) sustainability framework.

In conclusion, the outcomes of this research contribute valuable data and methodological insights to the emerging field of sustainable MOF production. The findings serve as a basis for process improvement within the SIMIACCI project and provide guidance for industry and academia in the development of next-generation filtration materials. As the need for sustainable air management in GLAM institutions continues to grow, materials such as MIL-100(Fe) could play a crucial role in reconciling conservation goals with environmental responsibility, provided that their production processes evolve toward higher efficiency, lower emissions, and circular resource use.

Ultimately, this thesis demonstrates that Life Cycle Assessment is not merely a diagnostic tool but a strategic instrument for innovation. By systematically identifying environmental hotspots and proposing targeted improvements, it lays the groundwork for the sustainable industrialization of advanced materials like MIL-100(Fe), fostering both technological progress and ecological sustainability.

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Appendix

Appendix A: Utilities data used in the Life Cycle Inventory dataset

Table A. 1: Supporting material used to calculate the utilities data.

	Reactor	Filter	Total	Total Flux	
Process water	254588 kg	44776 kg	299364 kg	6236.747227 kg/h	50143447.7 kg/year
	Reactor Flux	Filter Flux			
Process water	5303.911406 kg/h	932.8358209 kg/h			
	42643447.7 kg/year	7500000 kg/year			
	42643447702 g/year	7500000000 g/year			

	Reactor	Filter	Mill	Vessel
Electricity	5172675 Wh	16814 Wh	8266 Wh	11974 Wh
	5172.675376 kWh	16.81399699 kWh	8.265721561 kWh	11.97378559 kWh
	41588310.02 kWh/year	135184.5358 kWh/year	66456.40135 kWh/year	96269.23616 kWh/year

	Dryer	Other Steps	Total Flux	Total Flux
Vapour	3423 kg/h	17568 kg/h	20991 kg/h	168769047.4 kg/year
	27520474.77 kg/year	141248572.6 kg/year		
	27520474769 g/year	1.41249E+11 g/year		

Appendix B: Model developed for MIL-100(Fe) production process in SimaPro

Table B.1: Reaction data SimaPro

Reaction		
Materials/fuels	Value	Units
Iron sulfate {RER} market for iron sulfate Cut-off, U	752889.1	kg
Water, completely softened {RER} market for water, completely softened Cut-off, U	625003.8	kg
BTC	709254.6	kg
Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for oxygen, liquid Cut-off, U	26433.45	kg
Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	66080.31	kg
Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	42643448	kg
Electricity/heat		
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	41588310	kWh
Emissions to air		
Oxygen	1850.272	kg
Waste to treatment		
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	569.6608	m ³
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	63.51693	m ³
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	42643.45	m ³
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	452.079	m ³
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	52.70224	m ³
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	66.08031	m ³
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	35.32286478	m ³

Table B. 2: SimaPro data of filtration, drying and milling steps of the production process of MIL-100(Fe)

Filtration

Materials/fuels	Value	Units
Water, completely softened {RER} market for water, completely softened Cut-off, U	7500000	kg
Waste to treatment		
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	7200	m ³

Drying

Materials/fuels	Value	Units
Water, completely softened {RER} market for water, completely softened Cut-off, U	300000	kg
Heat, from steam, in chemical industry {RER} market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry Cut-off, U	75569297.28	MJ
Waste to treatment		
Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} market for wastewater, average Cut-off, U	300	m ³

Milling

Electricity/heat	Value	Units
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	66456.40135	kWh

Appendix C: Results Analysis

Table C. 1: Normalised values of the input and output flows in the reaction step, illustrating their relative contribution to the environmental impact categories of the EF 3.1 (adapted) method.

Damage category	FeSO ₄ ^(a)	H ₂ O, softened ^(b)	BTC	Oxygen ^(c)	NaOH ^(d)	H ₂ O, deionised ^(e)	Electricity ^(f)	Wastewater ^(g)
Eutrophication, freshwater	5.82E+01	8.85E-02	2.61E+02	6.76E+00	2.64E+01	4.15E+00	7.47E+03	4.69E+01
Resource use, fossils	3.28E+01	5.85E-02	6.35E+02	4.45E+00	1.49E+01	3.47E+00	4.90E+03	3.00E+00
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	1.86E+01	2.74E-01	2.08E+03	6.67E-01	1.31E+01	3.86E+01	7.22E+02	6.79E+01
Ionising radiation	1.02E+01	2.23E-02	5.33E+01	1.90E+00	3.82E+00	5.05E-01	2.11E+03	6.77E-01
Human toxicity, cancer	5.92E+01	6.18E-02	3.30E+02	1.50E+00	3.97E+01	7.37E+00	1.56E+03	1.02E+01
Climate change	1.56E+01	2.46E-02	1.78E+02	1.63E+00	7.79E+00	2.30E+00	1.79E+03	2.23E+00
Acidification	1.59E+01	1.66E-02	9.68E+01	1.13E+00	4.91E+00	3.32E+00	1.23E+03	1.48E+00
Photochemical ozone formation	1.20E+01	1.22E-02	1.48E+02	7.81E-01	4.08E+00	1.38E+00	8.39E+02	1.38E+00
Human toxicity, non-cancer	3.31E+01	1.53E-02	8.32E+01	7.37E-01	6.32E+00	1.97E+00	8.00E+02	2.04E+01
Resource use, minerals and metals	9.56E+01	2.21E-02	1.40E+02	4.55E-01	1.37E+01	3.66E+00	4.62E+02	1.35E+00
Eutrophication, marine	7.42E+00	8.52E-03	4.61E+01	5.63E-01	2.96E+00	7.37E-01	6.09E+02	3.57E+01
Eutrophication, terrestrial	8.62E+00	8.54E-03	5.04E+01	5.45E-01	2.94E+00	8.12E-01	5.85E+02	1.44E+00
Particulate matter	1.07E+01	9.13E-03	6.29E+01	3.84E-01	3.66E+00	2.45E+00	4.03E+02	1.59E+00
Water use	2.59E+00	2.69E+00	6.37E+01	2.35E+00	1.84E+00	1.65E+02	3.13E+02	-1.64E+02
Land use	1.34E+00	1.06E-03	4.66E+00	6.14E-02	3.46E-01	9.13E-02	6.61E+01	1.04E-01
Ozone depletion	3.82E-02	1.76E-03	1.98E+00	4.07E-03	6.53E-02	1.25E-01	4.46E+00	3.80E-03

(a) Iron sulfate {RER} market for iron sulfate | Cut-off, S

(b) Water, completely softened {RER} market for water, completely softened | Cut-off, S

(c) Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for oxygen, liquid | Cut-off, S

(d) Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state | Cut-off, S

(e) Water, deionised {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionised | Cut-off, S

(f) Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage | Cut-off, S

(g) Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment | Cut-off, S

Table C. 2: Normalised values of the input and output flows in the drying step, illustrating their relative contribution to the environmental impact categories of the EF 3.1 (adapted) method.

Damage category	H₂O, softened^(a)	Heat^(b)	Wastewater^(c)
Resource use, fossils	2.81E-02	1.86E+03	1.77E-02
Human toxicity, cancer	2.96E-02	1.31E+03	4.03E-02
Climate change	1.18E-02	1.12E+03	1.33E-02
Eutrophication, freshwater	4.25E-02	5.62E+02	2.42E-01
Photochemical ozone formation	5.86E-03	4.87E+02	8.01E-03
Acidification	7.98E-03	4.09E+02	9.39E-03
Particulate matter	4.38E-03	4.07E+02	7.70E-03
Eutrophication, terrestrial	4.10E-03	2.20E+02	9.43E-03
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	1.32E-01	2.18E+02	2.42E-01
Eutrophication, marine	4.09E-03	1.90E+02	2.79E-01
Human toxicity, non-cancer	7.35E-03	1.86E+02	1.56E-01
Ionising radiation	1.07E-02	4.65E+01	5.04E-03
Resource use, minerals and metals	1.06E-02	4.30E+01	7.56E-03
Water use	1.29E+00	1.91E+01	-1.12E+00
Land use	5.08E-04	9.97E+00	6.42E-04
Ozone depletion	8.44E-04	4.80E+00	1.99E-05

(a) Water, completely softened {RER}| market for water, completely softened | Cut-off, S

(b) Heat, from steam, in chemical industry {RER}| market for heat, from steam, in chemical industry | Cut-off, S

(c) Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland}| treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment | Cut-off, S

Table C. 3: Comparison of normalised environmental impacts for the production of MIL-100(Fe) and HEPA filter material (glass fibre) according to the EF 3.1 (adapted) method.

Damage category	Production process of MIL-100(Fe)	Production process of HEPA material
Eutrophication, freshwater	8.46E+03	4.05E+02
Resource use, fossils	7.46E+03	5.18E+02
Human toxicity, cancer	3.33E+03	3.57E+02
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	3.17E+03	1.36E+02
Climate change	3.13E+03	2.83E+02
Ionising radiation	2.23E+03	8.78E+01
Acidification	1.77E+03	2.89E+02
Photochemical ozone formation	1.50E+03	2.64E+02
Human toxicity, non-cancer	1.14E+03	9.87E+02
Eutrophication, marine	9.00E+02	1.67E+02
Particulate matter	8.92E+02	1.71E+02
Eutrophication, terrestrial	8.71E+02	1.95E+02
Resource use, minerals and metals	7.61E+02	4.59E+03
Water use	4.13E+02	5.72E+01
Land use	8.28E+01	7.06E+00
Ozone depletion	1.15E+01	9.72E-01

Table C. 4: Comparison of normalised environmental impacts for the production of MIL-100(Fe) and MERV-13 filter material (polypropylene granulate) according to the EF 3.1 (adapted) method.

Damage category	Production process of MIL-100(Fe)	Production process of MERV-13 material
Eutrophication, freshwater	8.46E+03	2.65E+02
Resource use, fossils	7.46E+03	1.16E+03
Human toxicity, cancer	3.33E+03	5.23E+02
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	3.17E+03	1.46E+02
Climate change	3.13E+03	3.13E+02
Ionising radiation	2.23E+03	4.02E+01
Acidification	1.77E+03	1.29E+02
Photochemical ozone formation	1.50E+03	3.14E+02
Human toxicity, non-cancer	1.14E+03	1.53E+02
Eutrophication, marine	9.00E+02	7.27E+01
Particulate matter	8.92E+02	9.51E+01
Eutrophication, terrestrial	8.71E+02	8.31E+01
Resource use, minerals and metals	7.61E+02	3.32E+02
Water use	4.13E+02	9.63E+01
Land use	8.28E+01	8.16E+00
Ozone depletion	1.15E+01	2.06E+00